

Middle East University

Faculty of Education

SCHOOL CLIMATE AND STUDENTS' INTENTION
TO LEAVE SCHOOL: A CASE STUDY

A Thesis

Presented in Partial Fulfillment of the

Requirements for the Degree

Master of Arts in Education

by

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June 2020

THESIS ABSTRACT

Master of Arts in Education and School Supervision

Middle East University

Faculty of Education

Title: SCHOOL CLIMATE AND STUDENTS' INTENTION TO LEAVE
SCHOOL: A CASE STUDY

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Date Completed: May 2020

The number of students leaving the Evangelical Heritage School (EHS) has taken on a yearly pattern of about 20 students between the academic year 2011-2012 and 2018-2019. Students leave school as they reach the intermediate and the secondary level, even though many of them had been enrolled in the school since kindergarten. To research the reasons, 171 students from Grade 7 till 12, were surveyed and 10 students were interviewed. The survey included 12 demographic questions related to students and 30 quantitative questions about school climate. The survey contained a section where students were free to express what they feel the survey did not address. The qualitative answers of this section and the interviews were classified, coded, and added to the data. The data from the survey and the interviews showed that the high academic level of the school in Secondary classes was pressuring students who showed intention to leave to another school. Also, the data showed that the students' experience was not satisfactory due to the absence of some

physical aspects such as library, labs, and after-school Activities. Finally, the qualitative answers supported the quantitative responses in showing that one important aspect of school climate that was driving students to intend to leave school was the teachers' attitude.

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

LIST OF FIGURES	ix
ACKNOWLEDGMENTS	xi
Chapter	
1. INTRODUCTION	1
Statement of the Problem.....	3
Purpose of the Study	3
Research Questions.....	4
Definition of Terminology.....	4
List of Abbreviations	5
2. LITERATURE REVIEW.....	6
Defining School Climate	7
Factors that Affect School Climate.....	8
The Student Factor	8
The Parent Factor	9
The Teacher Factor.....	9
The Academic Factor	10
The Extracurricular Activities Factor.....	11
The School Style Factor	11
The School Physical Factor	13
The School Size Factor.....	14
The Socio-Economic Factor	15
Research on School Culture, Retention, and Early School Leaving	16
Tools for Measuring School Climate.....	18
The Conceptual Framework of the Study	19
3. METHODOLOGY	20
Research Design	20
Data Collection Methods	20
Population and Sample	21
Instruments	21
Procedures.....	24
Data Analysis.....	24
Ethical Consideration.....	26

4. DATA ANALYSIS	27
Demographics of the Study	27
The Four Domains of School Climate	34
Four Domains Correlation Test	35
Personal/Social Environment	36
Physical Environment.....	44
The Learning/Cognitive Environment.....	51
Moral Environment	57
Student Satisfaction	65
Intention to Leave.....	66
Analysis of Qualitative Responses	67
Summary of Qualitative Section in SSS.....	67
Summary of the Interviews	69
Step by Step Graph Analysis of the Data to Answer the Research Questions ..	77
Step 1: The Effect of Demographics on Student Satisfaction.	79
Step 2: Cross-Tabulating Future Variable “I’m Leaving EHS” with	
Satisfaction	81
Step 3: Correlation between the Four Domains as Variables and	
Satisfaction	82
Step 4: Cross-Tabulation and Regression between Demographics and	
Future Status (Intention to Leave EHS)	84
Step 5: Cross-Tabulation and Correlation Between I’m leaving EHS	
and the Four Domains	88
5. CONCLUSION	91
Summary and Conclusions	91
Responding to Research Questions	92
Limitations.....	96
Recommendations.....	96
Recommendations for Further Research	99
REFERENCES.....	101
APPENDICES.....	107
A. SCHOOL SATISFACTION SURVEY (SSS).....	107
B. INTERVIEW QUESTIONS	110
C. INTERVIEW RESPONSES	111
D. LIST OF 30 QUESTIONS: INDEPENDENT AND DEPENDENT.....	114

LIST OF TABLES

1. Number of Students Surveyed.....	21
2. Reliability Statistics.....	22
3. Reliability Statistics for Each of the Four Domains.....	23
4. Mean Indicator	25
5. Gender Representation and Number of Participants	28
6. Parents' Educational Level.....	29
7. Parents' Yearly Income	30
8. Class and Level of Starting School	32
9. Mean Indicator	35
10. Correlations of the Four Domains of School Climate.....	36
11. Students in Cycle 3 and Secondary	58
12. Mean Indicator	62
13. Summary Item Statistics of SSS.....	63
14. The Top 5 Most Influential Positive Questions	64
15. Most Negative Answers	65
16. Number of Remarks in the Qualitative Section of the SSS.....	68
17. Totals of the Positive, Negative, and Moderate Feedback.....	69
18. Interview Question. What is Your Definition of a Good School? Do You See Your school Like That?	72
19. Interview Question. Describe Your School Atmosphere. Welcoming, Safe, Pressing, Demanding.....	72
20. Interview Question. What One Thing You Like Most About Your School?.....	73
21. Interview Question. How do You See the School Rules and Regulations?....	73
22. Interview Question. What Subject Do You Enjoy Most? Why?.....	74
23. Interview Question. What Has Been Most Challenging to You in This School and Why?	75
24. Interview Question. In What Words Do You Describe Your Teachers and Your Relationship with Them?	75
25. Interview Question. Would You Recommend this School to a Friend or Relative and Why?.....	76

26. Interview Question. What is the One Thing You Would Like to Change in Your School?.....	76
27. Interview Question. If You Were Given the Chance to Leave to Another School, Would You Go? What Would be the Reason?.....	77
28. Regression Method on Satisfaction Against Demographics	80
29. Cross-tabulation between Satisfaction and Future	82
30. Correlation Table with 4 Variables Regarding Students Leaving EHS	83
31. Checking the Relationship between Student Satisfaction and the Four Domains	83
32. Cross-Tabulation and Regression between Demographics and Future Status just for those Have Intention to Leave EHS).....	85
33. Cross-tabulation between Demographics and Leaving the EHS.....	85
34. Checking the Significance between Class vs. Four Domains as Variables	86
35. Checking the Significance between Education vs. Four Domains as Variables.....	87
36. Cross-tabulation between Future and Rank	88
37. Means of the Ten Leaving Students on the Four Domains	89
38. Regression between 4 Domains and “Leaving EHS”	89
39. Correlation of the Ten Leaving Students with the Four Domains	90

LIST OF FIGURES

1. Conceptual framework of the study	19
2. Student participation according to class.....	28
3. When students joined the school.....	32
4. Students' grading and rank in class.....	33
5. Mean results for each domain of SSS	34
6. Personal/Social Environment means.....	37
7. Responses to Personal/Social question "I feel EHS is my home"	38
8. Responses to Personal/Social question "I'm treated as an individual".....	39
9. Responses to Personal/Social question "I'm in good relationship with my teachers"	39
10. Responses to Personal/Social question "open, honest and active communication occurs between teachers-students, and teachers-parents"	41
11. Responses to Personal/Social question "my family considers EHS warm, inviting and helpful"	41
12. Responses to Personal/Social question "my parents are proud of EHS results in the official exams"	42
13. Responses to Personal/Social question "EHS has good reputation in the community".....	43
14. Responses to Personal/Social question "in the future, I will enroll my children at EHS"	44
15. Physical Environment means.....	45
16. Responses to Physical question "classrooms and grounds are clean and well- maintained"	45
17. Responses to Physical question "school and classrooms are rich with displays of works created by students"	46
18. Responses to Physical question "I'm satisfied with EHS library".....	47
19. Responses to Physical question "I'm satisfied with EHS playground"	48
20. Responses to Physical question "I'm satisfied with EHS labs".....	49
21. Responses to physical question "the canteen provides what I need".....	49
22. Responses to Physical question "Students feel safe everywhere on EHS property"	50

23. Responses to Physical question “EHS rules and regulations regarding safety and expected behavior are clear”	51
24. Learning/Cognitive Environment means	52
25. Responses to Learning/Cognitive question “Students are encouraged to succeed”	52
26. Responses to Learning/Cognitive question “EHS educational level is very high”	53
27. Responses to Learning/Cognitive question “achievements and performance are rewarded, praised and publicly displayed”	54
28. Responses to Learning/Cognitive question “students are assigned to research, prepare a presentation, and present in class”	54
29. Responses to Learning/Cognitive question “progress is monitored, evaluated regularly, and shared with parents”	55
30. Responses to Learning/Cognitive question “I’m satisfied with afterschool activities”	56
31. Responses to Learning/Cognitive question “teachers are caring and supportive”	57
32. Moral environment means	58
33. Responses to Moral question “EHS values diversity and is welcoming to all cultures”	59
34. Responses to Moral question “EHS has built my character with values and respect”	60
35. Responses to Moral question “staff, students, and families demonstrate school pride”	61
36. Responses to Moral question “EHS and its educational program include development of knowledge/skills that promote ethical decision-making and conflict resolution”	62
37. Responses to Moral question “I’m satisfied with my experience at EHS”	65
38. Students’ feedback about their future education at EHS	66
39. Step by step analysis of the data to answer the research questions.....	78
40. The conceptual framework and the main results of the analysis	95

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

I would like to thank The Lord God for it is “by the grace of God I am what I am, and his grace to me was not without effect” (1 Cor 15:10).

Also, I would like to thank God for my wife Katia and my daughters Jennifer and Andrea for the ongoing support and encouragement throughout the time of the thesis.

I am thankful to the Evangelical Heritage School for providing the field of study and making the Principal’s report available.

Finally, I would also like to thank my thesis advisor Dr. John Issa and the thesis committee Dr. Carlos Biaggi and Dr. Shawna Vyhmeister for extensive personal and professional guidance which helped me discover, learn, and enjoy the work.

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

The fact that students are leaving private schools is becoming an increasingly alarming situation in Lebanon. According to the UNESCO Institute of Statistics (BankMed, 2014) the percentage of students leaving private schools in 2012 reached 6.7% at the primary level, while at the intermediate level it reached 17.3%. These figures reflect a critical worry for the educational system in Lebanon. However, students leaving school is not limited to Lebanon only. In 1993, in spite of all efforts and high expectations that all students will graduate from high school in the USA, about 3.4 million of 30.8 million students had not completed high school as reported by the National Center for Education Statistics (Hess & Copeland, 2001). The findings of the *Longitudinal Survey of Australian Youth* (LSAY), a project conducted over 9 years, revealed that students' attitudes towards their school life experience have an implication on students' achievements and students' decision of leaving school (Marks, 1998). In 2014, in Poland, the problem of early school leaving reached 5.6% (Wrona, Malkowska-Szkutnik, & Tomaszewska-Pekala, 2015). Governments and local institutions in EU countries are aware of early school leaving reaching as high as 15.7% in 2015, as the CARMA (n.d.) report indicates. Facing such a problem led the EU to put a strategy to reduce the proportion of early school leavers (ESL) to less than 10% by year 2020 (Gillies & Mifsud, 2016).

In the case of the Evangelical Heritage School (EHS)¹, a pseudonym given due to the nature of the sensitive information used, operates in Lebanon (in Beirut and its suburbs), student leaving school has taken on a yearly pattern of about 20 students between the academic year 2011-2012 and 2018-2019. In spite of the long history in education and the high standard achievements, EHS is still dropping in numbers. This situation has lead the administration to examine the reasons in order to indicate the areas that need improvement.

The Evangelical Heritage School (EHS) is a school in Beirut founded by the American Mission in the early 1920s, initially as an elementary school for girls. In the early 1950s, the first elementary school graduates received the Lebanese Certificat. Following that, the first secondary school graduate received diplomas known as the Baccalaureate. EHS became a notable school and its graduates were accepted at the American University of Beirut (AUB) and the Beirut University College (LAU now) without entrance exams. During the war the school was displaced to different places around Beirut and its suburbs and became a mixed gender school from K to 12. The Evangelical Heritage School has now approximately 700 students, 80 teachers, and 40 staff. EHS, being built on Christian principles, continues its role in education guided by the founders' vision to provide education to all people and prepare students to be good and open-minded citizens.

For EHS and many other schools, student retention has become a persisting challenge facing principals. The value of this research is that it sheds light on this problem and aims to investigate the reasons and find solutions for it.

¹Since the institution was given a pseudonym, the following part relating to its history and other details will remain with no citation/reference.

Statement of the Problem

There is an increasing number of students who leave school and do not register the following year although they had been enrolled in that school since kindergarten (Candal & Ardon, 2017). This has been the case for the Evangelical Heritage School (EHS) as well, where in the past four or five years, the percentage of students leaving has increased, even though many of the leaving students had been enrolled in the school since kindergarten. Moreover, the concern of the administration at EHS has been to find out the reasons and suggest solutions as to why students leave school as they reach the intermediate level and most importantly when they reach the secondary level or high school. The decrease in the number of students is affecting the financial capacity of the school, especially after the issuing of Law 46/2017 (Baroud, 2019), the Salary Scale law which implements an increase in teacher salaries.

Purpose of the Study

This paper aims to examine the causes of student leaving EHS and provide a clear assessment of the school climate which seems to affect student satisfaction at EHS and further suggest some recommendations. The focus of this research is the reasons why students have intention to leave EHS regardless of where they eventually go; to another private school, public school, travel, or if they fully drop out.

It is worth noting that this research is not concerned with students who leave during the school year for traveling reasons or emergency situations in the family as they are very few. Our focus is on why some EHS students have intention to leave school regardless if they want to leave to another school or drop out.

Research Questions

The concerns of the administration are focused on the following variables: increase in tuition costs, teacher-student relationship, school policies and regulations, difficulty with the curriculum, and the physical environment. In other words, this research will answer the following research questions:

1. Which of the following demographics: grade level, family status, family income, years of continuous education, means of transportation, and student rank affect student satisfaction resulting in students intention to leave EHS?
2. What is the relationship between each of the following school climate domains and student satisfaction: (1) Personal/Social Environment, (2) Physical Environment, (3) Learning/Cognitive Environment, and (4) Moral Environment?
3. What factors of school climate or demographics at EHS are associated with student intention to leave school?

Definition of Terminology

Student Retention: The number of students who remain enrolled until they graduate (Voigt & Hundrieser, 2008).

Drop-out: Students who leave school/university for good before graduation without enrolling in another school (Bonneau, 2008).

Push out: Students leave school as a consequence of factors inside the school (Doll, Eslami, & Walters, 2013).

Pull out: Students leave school as a consequence of factors outside the school (Doll et al., 2013).

List of Abbreviations

Throughout this research, the *Evangelical Heritage School* will be referred to as EHS and the *Student Satisfaction Survey* which will be used to collect data will be referred to as SSS. Also, SPSS is used to refer to the *Statistical Package for Social Sciences*; a program used to perform statistical operations to provide results.

CHAPTER 2

LITERATURE REVIEW

In the Literature Review section, we will research what has been written about school climate and what factors may affect it positively or negatively. We will start with the stakeholders of school climate starting from the student, to the parent, and then the teacher. Then we will research the school as a factor itself to move into the outside factors that may play a role in student intention to leave the school. Also, we will summarize research on School Culture, Retention, and Early School Leaving. Finally, we will look at available instruments used to measure the school climate. So, to categorize our readings we will start with the definition of school climate and divide the factors into nine factors as follows:

1. The Student factor
2. The Parent Factor
3. The Teacher Factor
4. The Academic Factor
5. The Extracurricular Activities Factor
6. The School Style Factor
7. The School Physical Factor
8. The School Size Factor
9. The Socio-Economic Factor

In the end of the literature review we will research the different measuring tools or instruments to follow the best procedure in preparing our own measuring tool.

Also, a conceptual framework for the study is developed in order to answer the research questions in a logical, clear, and step by step manner.

Defining School Climate

School climate is a wide notion that describes “the quality and character of school life”, the student experience, the teachers’ satisfaction, and on a larger definition it is the sphere of school life (Cohen, McCabe, Michelli, & Pickeral, 2009, p. 182). Tagiuri (1968) defines school climate as the quality of the environment. Students live within a school climate formed of the school learning atmosphere and the physical environment such as classrooms, play areas, labs, libraries, and public areas. They follow written and unwritten school rules and policies, meet deadlines, and comply with the school set of values, norms, and goals that are part of the school climate. Peterson and Deal (1998) argue that school climate impacts a whole lot of schools and what happens within: the way teachers treat students, the way instructions are carried out, and the emphasis given to student learning. School climate is summarized by the feeling of safety and the “sense” of belonging to the school (Community Matters, 2018). Moreover, the school climate is what differentiates one school from another school (Raman, Chi Ling, & Khalid, 2015).

Freiberg and Stein (1999) defines school climate as the spirit of the school that attracts students to love their school and become part of it. It depends on how much students and parents are satisfied with their school. For students to stay in one school and finish successfully involves providing a caring and supporting climate to meet the academic standards. According to researchers, a positive school climate increases attendance, achievement, retention, and even rates of graduation (Cohen & Geier, 2010).

Factors that Affect School Climate

There are factors that affect the school climate whether positively or negatively and among these factors are the human factor such as the student, parents, and teachers. Other factors belong to the school itself such as its academics, extracurricular activities, and its managerial style. The school physical environment and its size also play a role in shaping the climate. Last but not least, among many other factors, the socio-economic status of the students' families affects the school climate.

The Student Factor

Student attitudes towards school are an important indicator of whether students will stay or leave school. Hence, students with positive experiences are less likely to leave their school than students with negative experiences, even if both are doing well academically (Marks, 1998). So to avoid the negative experiences, it is important to survey Intermediate, Middle, and High school students on their perceptions of school climate as they are now able to express how they feel about it (Thapa, Cohen, Guffey & Higgins-D' Alessandro, 2013).

Students who have poor relationships with their peers and their teachers are more likely to have disruptive behaviors and become disconnected from school (Bond et al., 2007). Also, research have found that students' negative experience at school or dissatisfaction, including being bullied, low achievement, stress, not getting along with their teachers, feeling unwelcomed, and feeling lack of secure, will end up in less connectedness to school, more interpersonal conflict, and the use of substances such as drugs (Bond et al., 2007). Students develop close interpersonal relationships with their classmates, teachers, and the school as they move from class to class over the years (Alspaugh, 1998).

The Parent Factor

Many parents choose what school they will send their children to, based on the parents' perceptions of school climate (Schueler et al., 2014). That is why they look for a school that is good in outlook and education (Khan & Qureshi, 2010). If parents are convinced of the school, they then can get their children become excited about learning, continuing, and even finishing school as children like to follow their parents' example (Kainuwa, & Yusuf, 2013). Gratz, Nation, Schools, & Kurth-Schai (2006) argue that parents have a strong impact on their children's education whether positively or negatively, and the more parents are educated the more they influence their kids positively to peruse education. Also, mothers with high education specifically, influence children to stay in school and seek higher education as they give more time to follow-up on their children so that they will receive good quality education. On the other hand, parents' attitudes that show indifference to their children's education are highly correlated with negative school outcome. Moreover, some research show that parents with low-income are generally less involved with their children's education, yet other research shows that this had an insignificant effect on their children's success in education (Gratz, Nation, Schools & Kurth-Schai, 2006).

Parents' perceptions of school climate are more positive when their kids are young than when their kids grow older and move into higher classes. Increasingly, students and parents are more and more into having a "say-so" about their school facilities and performance (Stevenson, 2001).

The Teacher Factor

Christle, Jolivette, and Nelson (2007) argue that inexperienced and unqualified teachers' behavior have a great influence on students' wanting to stay in school or

leave. Moreover, teachers are role models to students second to their parents, and the positive characteristics of the teachers may encourage a student to stay in school and even achieve better. It is about how teachers establish positive partnership with parents that will increase school involvement (Knopf & Swick, 2007).

Feldlaufer et al (1988) claims that when teachers support and demand high expectations from their students, they encourage and make their students feel more competent and engaged. Furthermore, such a climate produce better performance, and consequently less likely to have increased drop outs of school. On the other side, Janosz (as cited in Jia et al., 2015) confirms that “a pattern of low expectations and low engagement can lead to repeated academic failure, alienation, and eventual dropout from school” (p. 10).

A qualitative study involving 132 school leavers conducted by The Youth Research Center confirms that most of those students who have left school are because of their dissatisfaction with their teachers (McMillan & Marks, 2003).

The Academic Factor

Leaving school can give an early sign, as early as Grade 3 and on (Bowers 2017). According to Boday (2013), students from preschool till Grade 3 learn to read while after Grade 3 students read to learn. Also, school readiness and Grade 3 reading proficiency can serve as indicators of school completion. The main factor of students leaving school is the student performance (Marks, 2007). Dropping out of high school is not an impulsive decision but rather a termination of a long-term process of a student’s disengagement as early as first grade (Christle, Jolivette, & Nelson, 2007).

Alexander, Entwisle, Kabbani (2001), as sited by Hughes, Cao, West, Smith, and Cerda (2017), argue that low academic achievement in lower grades such as grade one, is strongly correlated with failing in elementary classes and leaving school by

age 16. Legally, students can leave school by age 16 to go to work full time and can enroll in a private school or home schooling at the same time (Hughes et al., 2017). Also, Alexander et al. (2003) have found that staying in the same grade does not hinder children academically or hurt their self-esteem in early years, but rather that their experience have weakened their attachment to school, thus they decide to leave school as an easy “exit” as Hughes et al. (2017) call it. Although repeating a grade will help failing students boost academically, such students reach a point when they find middle grades demanding and start to struggle and this will affect their commitment to stay in school (Alexander, Entwisle, & Dauber, 2003).

The Extracurricular Activities Factor

Morton et al. (2016) argue that data from different schools in different countries show that the amount of physical activity decreases throughout childhood and into adolescence. In other words, students in primary level are more involved in activities during school time and after-school, while middle and increasingly secondary students are more likely to have light physical activity and most of the time in sedentary mode. Also, several studies show that transition from primary level to secondary level is marked by big change in activities and programs (Morton et al., 2016). Students with low academic performance, low attendance, and low involvement in extracurricular activities constitute a large percentage of students who eventually leave school (Freeman & Simonsen, 2015).

The School Style Factor

Freeman and Simonsen (2015) argue that although schools cannot change students’ demographics such as percentage of students who come from low-income and minority families, and others come from urban areas, yet schools will have to

appropriately deal with such concerns that are out of school control. However, an authoritative climate in the school can decrease such demographic risks and improve student engagement at school. An authoritative high school climate that provides support to students has less truancy and fewer dropouts than authoritarian, permissive, or neglectful high school climate (Jia, 2015). For a school to retain its students there should be a major change in the school structure where it becomes more of a student-oriented school that caters for all students rather than an academic-oriented school (Christle, Jolivette, & Nelson, 2007). Schools should provide students with a tool or a mechanism so their voices could be heard. Students' voices and feedback could inform decisions and implement improvements not only to benefit the school but to provide the students with a better experience (Shah & Nair, 2009). School administrations use data systems to identify prospect leaving students (Freeman & Simonsen, 2015).

Marks (1998) argues that the influence of the school on its student satisfaction is the school itself, as students stay in the same school surrounded by the same physical environment, and deal daily with the same teachers under the same school authority. Several studies have showed that schools themselves may create conditions and practices that *push* certain types of students *out* of school (Lee & Burkam, 2003). There are also external factors that *pull* certain types of students *out* of school, such as financial need, family factors, jobs, etc. (Doll et al., 2013). The school is the major factor of students' *push out* while the major factor of *pull out* is the student. Some research have shown that students leaving school is a result of *push out* rather than *pull out* factors. Students resolve their problems with their school by leaving school (Lee & Burkam, 2003).

Schools are under “measure pressure” to measure their students’ high school exit exams and to measure the school performance, and both of these add more reasons for weak and struggling students to leave school (Hemelt & Marcotte, 2013). A similar type of pressure exists in the Lebanese case where schools put their students under competing situations where they need to have 100% success in the official exams and to compete with other schools.

Some schools implement what is called “Exit Interview” or “Withdrawal Interview” with those who were leaving. This kind of interview will help the school gather information on the reasons of leaving and will show that the school really cares for its students, even for those who are leaving (Voigt & Hundrieser, 2008).

The School Physical Factor

Maiden and Foreman (1998), as cited in McGowan (2007) note that “the behavior of students is often driven by how they perceive their surroundings, including their physical environment” (pp. 29-30). Schneider (2002) argues that well-maintained classrooms, indoor air quality, ventilation, thermal comfort, temperature and humidity, lighting, and acoustics can produce either comfort or irritation. He also argues that school building age, aesthetics including color, and quality of facilities have an impact on students’ behaviors and attitudes.

Bowers and Burkett (1989) have compare schools with age difference of 44 years and have found out that students prefer modern schools and consequently attendance came to be higher (McGowan, 2007). Facilities encourage the community to keep on supporting the school initiatives and encourage students to stay at school and behave properly until graduation (Deal & Peterson, 2016). On the other hand, the library, for example, should be designed in a way to include books and other media formats to create a space that is functional and inspirational (Stewart, 2018). Since the

school is a social system, improving one part of its physical aspect will reflect on other aspects; and enhancing the school's performance in academics and extracurricular activities will increase the competitive advantage to attract new students and to create a sense of belongingness (Khan & Qureshi, 2010).

Wright (1997) argues that integrating technology in schools and providing real life applications in the classroom decreases dropout rates (Schneider, 2002).

McGowan (2007) claims that research show more and more that school facilities are a reason to leaving school. Working on the school climate can be used as a good strategy to prevent students from leaving school (Thapa et al., 2013). School components or aspects should arrange for enhanced school environment that invites the students for more positive engagement that leads to secondary level completion (Bond et al., 2007).

The School Size Factor

Research on the effect of small schools has shown that dropout rates are less in high schools with smaller enrollment. Cotton (1996) argues that small size schools of 600 to 800 students provide relevant conditions such as: sense of belonging, social bonding with teachers, and increased teachers' attention, that keep students in the same school than do large size high schools. Students are able to create a personal bond with their teachers, staff, and with the physical environment (McGowan, 2007). Moreover, Gregory and Smith (1987) state that "students in a small high school experience an increasingly more positive attitude toward school" (as cited in Cotton, 1996, p. 5). Small high schools in rural areas with a grade span from 7 to 12 have the lowest rate of dropouts as students build close interpersonal relationships over the years with their peers and teachers (Alspaugh, 1998). In small schools, parents feel more involved, since they tend to know the principal more closely and can easily

communicate with teachers in terms of following up on their children's progress (Cotton, 1996).

Nathan and Febey (2001) as well as Schneider (2002), argue that smaller schools afford a safer, more positive, and challenging atmosphere where students have limited behavioral problems, achieve higher, and are more likely to graduate in higher rates. Bowers (2017) claims that studies have found that in a small-size school students have more chances to participate in athletic activities and extracurricular activities. Thus investing money in school activities has a positive outcome as to strengthen students' attachment to school (Alspaugh, 1998). Students who develop a sense of belonging and connectedness to the school are less likely to leave school (Christle, Jolivette, & Nelson, 2007).

The Socio-Economic Factor

Schools with students from low socioeconomic status have higher rates of dropouts, which is another form of leaving school. Such students face challenging circumstances that make attending school and achievement difficult (Jia, Konold, & Cornell, 2015). Low school and social connectedness are associated with school incompleteness (Bond et al., 2007).

In a study that answered the question, what causes a 21st century high school student to leave school? Leaving school has never been a spontaneous decision but rather a difficult one, and usually comes as a result of a long struggle the student have experienced at school (Bowers, 2017). The data from Bower's (2017) survey and from interviewing those who left school (former students aged 16-32 years old) showed years of academic and social struggle that led to such decision.

On the other hand, Marks (1998) claims that a family's socioeconomic status have a minimal effect on students liking their school; its effect is significant on achievement, which has a moderate effect on the decision of leaving school.

Research on School Culture, Retention, and Early School Leaving

To identify the dimensions of a supportive school culture and its effect on retention from students' perspective, 255 students of Grade 11 from two schools from the same district in Western Australia were surveyed (Gray & Hackling, 2009). The data were collected in three ways; through completing a survey in August 2006, followed by interviews with the Student Focus Groups in September- October 2007, and finally through using the school-based achievement report and retention at the end-of-Year 11 in February 2007 for each student. Participants linked academic success, positive experience, and retention with how much the school culture is supportive. A supportive school culture included students feeling engaged academically and socially. Respect, relationship and responsibility were three characteristics that impacted the decision making about retention. Students expressed school culture through their well-being and success. Around 76% of students consider the teacher to play an important role in supporting students to continue till graduation out of which 33% considered the teacher support to be very high. A total of 86% of the students considered their parents to their support out of which 40% considered their parent to be very high on support to continue their education. However, only 48% of the students considered their friends to be their support to continue at school. The survey came to the conclusion that students with a strong sense of social connectedness were more likely to stay at school beyond Grade 11 (Gray & Hackling, 2009).

In order to study the effect of school motivation, self-efficacy, students and parents' characteristics on school completion whether in academic or vocational track, 2,300 Grade 9 students of the academic year 2006-2007 participated in a longitudinal survey in Oslo, Norway (Daehlen, 2017). The study was concluded in the academic year 2009-2010. The study combined the results of the students' school performance with data from upper secondary school with information about the student's educational transitions history until the age of 21. The educational system in Norway consists of 10 compulsory years: 7 in primary level and 3 in lower secondary level, after which the students can continue their upper secondary level in either an academic or vocational track. One of the findings of the survey showed that the graduation rate from vocational schools was influenced to a greater extent by the students' school performance in a compulsory level in comparison with the graduation rate of their peers in the academic track. The survey concluded that school motivation and self-efficacy were positively related to completing high school (Daehlen, 2017).

To investigate whether school climate can predict the proportion of early school leavers, a study was done utilizing the database of the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) that included 170 principals and 4848 students. The findings came to show that the strongest predictor of early school leavers was teacher-related factors. These factors varied from teachers not encouraging students to their best and having low expectations of their students to having high levels of absenteeism among teachers. On the other hand, there were also student-related factors such as truancy, lacking respect for teachers, bullying, and discipline. However, teacher's morale and teacher-student-related factors came to have moderate effect on early school leavers (Ozmusul, 2016).

Tools for Measuring School Climate

There are different approaches to measure school climate, as school climate in itself is a heterogeneous concept (Kohl et al., 2013), and researchers may combine or adapt different validated instruments to produce a brief and concentrated instrument to measure specific domains (Zullig et al., 2017). A research study was carried out in Pretoria schools to measure the development of school climate. Six factors were selected for the study, namely (1) cohesiveness, (2) trust, (3) respect, (4) control, (5) violence and (6) physical infrastructure in a 65-items survey (Scherman, 2002).

To help administrations measure school climate, the National School Climate Center (NSCC) suggests the Comprehensive School Climate Inventory (CSCI) that measures five areas: (1) safety with focus on rules and norms, physical security, and social-emotional security (2) teaching and learning with focus on support for learning and social and civic learning (3) interpersonal relationships with focus on respect for diversity, social support—adults, and social support—students (4) institutional environment with focus on school connectedness- engagement and physical surroundings (5) staff only with focus on leadership and professional relationships (Durham et al., 2014). Durham et al. (2014) asserted that although different school climate instruments may be used, they all yield broadly similar conclusions.

Zullig et al. (2017) constructed The School Climate Measure (SCM) by selecting a combination of 39 questions on eight domains, chosen out of five instruments on climate measurements with 184 items. The subscales focused on the following 8 areas: 1) positive student-teacher relationships, with items such as “Teachers understand my problems” (9 items); 2) school connectedness (6 items); 3) academic support (6 items); 4) order and discipline (7 items); 5) physical environment (4 items); 6) social environment (2 items); 7) perceived exclusion/privilege, with

items such as “At my school, the same person always gets to help the teacher” (3 items); and 8) academic satisfaction (2 items).

In 2017, an educational organization known as GLSEN (the Gay, Lesbian and Straight Education Network), working to create safe and inclusive K-12 in United States schools, launched the first *National School Climate Survey* to examine whether the school had a hostile climate against LGBTQ students. The survey examined the educational outcomes and well-being of LGBTQ students, the school policies, and retention (GLSEN, 2019). Measuring school climate took a different approach from the classical ones.

Dary and Pickeral (2013) argued that choosing the best effective school climate assessment tool can be challenging, and that there were some factors needed to be well thought of to have the survey that would best fit the school situation.

The Conceptual Framework of the Study

The conceptual framework shown below in Figure 1 presents the variables of this study and the relationships that will be studied. The labels on the arrows indicate the research question (RQ) that this study will attempt to answer.

Figure 1. Conceptual framework of the study.

CHAPTER 3

METHODOLOGY

In this chapter, we looked into the research design, what methods had been followed to collect the data from students, and what instrument had been used. The target group was introduced in the population and sample section, and how they were involved in this research was explained in the procedure section. Also, we saw how the data were analyzed and what program was used for this purpose. At the end of the chapter, we would have an idea of how the whole process, from collecting the data till generating the results, were ethically considered.

Research Design

This research used a mixed methods case study design. It used quantitative and qualitative data to study why students had intention to leave school, and it studied the case of EHS.

Data Collection Methods

Three methods were used to generate data that could be analyzed. First, a survey was designed called *Student Satisfaction Survey (SSS)* from which we generated quantitative and qualitative data. Second, ten students were interviewed to provide additional qualitative data that the SSS might have missed. And third, the school made available the principal's reports and records for any additional information needed in order to compare and analyze, taking into consideration the ethical obligation.

Population and Sample

Next, I will describe the instruments, the population and sample, and the procedures used. The population of this case study is the 700 students of the Evangelical Heritage School (EHS), a secondary school in Kfarshima, a Beirut suburb. From this population, the sample included in this study is formed by 171 students from Grades 7-12, as shown in Table 1. All students participated in the survey questionnaire that examined their perception and satisfaction of school climate in four areas which were named as the four essential dimensions of school climate.

Table 1

Number of Students Surveyed

Number of Students per Class						
Grade 7	Grade 8	Grade 9	Grade 10	Grade 11	Grade 12	Total
29	33	18	35	36	20	171

Besides, 10 students from this sample were selected randomly for the interviews: five males and five females; two students from each grade: 7, 8, 9, 10, and 11.

Instruments

A survey instrument was constructed to measure the school climate at EHS (Appendix A). It was a combination of four instruments, however, the questions were edited to suit EHS situation: 1) the National Center for Community School (NCCS, n.d.), 2) Durham et al. (2014), 3) the National School Climate Center (NSCC, 2017), and 4) Scherman (2002), which best fit the school situation. The Student Satisfaction

Survey, abbreviated as SSS, was utilized to measure the students' perception and satisfaction on four essential domains of school climate: (1) Personal/Social Environment, (2) Physical Environment, (3) Learning/Cognitive Environment, and (4) Moral Environment (Appendix A). Nonetheless, each domain was composed of many questions, and the total number of questions was 30 of which 29 covered different areas of a specific domain and the last question measured the "student satisfaction." The researcher himself designed the questionnaire.

This approach had helped us understand the students' satisfaction with their school in order to improve the school's performance. Although the survey was precise and concise, it covered most subdomains mentioned in most of the surveys above to measure students' perspective and satisfaction about their school. The survey's measure of reliability through Cronbach's alpha indicated a high level of internal consistency for the SSS scale as a whole. Cronbach's Alpha (Gliem, 2003) is considered to be a measure of scale reliability, and technically speaking, it is not a statistical test but rather a coefficient of reliability (or consistency). Cronbach's Alpha can be written as a function of the number of test items and the average inter-correlation among the items (Gliem, 2003). The SSS reliability as a whole was 87.8%, as shown in the Table 2 below where Cronbach's alpha was 0.878.

Table 2

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of questions
.878	.879	30

Note. Reliability test score: 87.8%.

Also, internal consistency of every domain was very high as shown in Table 3. When Cronbach's Alpha $\alpha \geq 0.8$ then reliability is Excellent, $0.7 \leq \alpha < 0.8$ is Good, $0.6 \leq \alpha < 0.7$ is Acceptable, $0.5 \leq \alpha < 0.6$ is Questionable, while $\alpha < 0.5$ is Unacceptable reliability (Gliem, 2003).

The alpha coefficient for the four items was .874, suggesting that each domain separately had very high internal reliability and consistency. As for each domain, Cronbach's Alpha showed reliability .874 on the Personal/Social Environment domain, .875 on the Physical Environment domain, .875 on the Learning/Cognitive Environment domain, and .871 on the Moral Environment domain which were all considered excellent in consistency.

Table 3

Reliability Statistics for Each of the Four Domains

Cases	N	%
Valid	171	100.0
Excluded	0	.0
Total	171	100.0
Domains	Cronbach's Alpha	
AVG Personal/Social	.874	
AVG Physical	.875	
AVG Learn/Cognitive	.875	
AVG Moral	.871	
Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items	
.874	4	

The qualitative data was collected from two instruments. First, from the last question of the survey, which was an open-ended question labeled "My Remarks". Second, 10 random students were interviewed individually with an interview guide of

10 questions (see Appendix B) to get a deeper perspective from this sample. The interviews were recorded and then analyzed.

Procedures

For the survey, a brief introduction about the nature and purpose of the study, and the importance of the student engagement in such surveys was explicitly made to all students from Grade 7 till Grade 12 along with the emphasis on the anonymity of their answers. They were asked to provide some personal and family socio-demographical information such as gender, class, family status, family income, years of education, etc., without specifying their names or any type of identification data. The questionnaires were then distributed to participants who answered freely without any human interference. Finally, after filling the questionnaires, students dropped their responses in a closed box, rather than collecting the response sheets manually, for the sake of privacy, anonymity, and non-disclosure matters. In this procedure we assured the participants their privacy and anonymity in order to promote greater disclosure of needed information (Murdoch et al., 2014).

Data Analysis

Once all the 171 questionnaires of the Student Satisfaction Survey (SSS) were answered, they were counted and tallied for the purpose of identifying the true counts of respondents who participated in each class. The collected questionnaires were then entered into an excel sheet and handled by SPSS statistics program for the purpose of data management, processing, analyzing, and running statistical tests. The answers were sorted out in logical codes for SPSS to read the data and give error free results. The implementation of this program allowed full data reliability and transparency as

we were able to generate data in different ways in order to analyze and compare results.

The quantitative data generated from the Student Satisfaction Survey (SSS) were tabulated into a comprehensive statistical report (Total Sample). The survey consisted of 30 questions about how students felt towards different aspects. The scale used was Likert's five-scale Ladder where participants can chose one from "Strongly Disagree", "Disagree", "Neutral", "Agree", and "Strongly Agree" for every question. To analyze Likert's five-scale Ladder questions in the survey, SPSS Statistics 20 was used. Since only one school participated in the study, ANOVA was not employed, but rather Pearson correlation and regression were used. Descriptive analysis helped us find the frequencies, percentages, means, and standard deviations; it was the most suitable and valuable statistical procedure in this case. The Mean Indicator helped in the analysis of the data by looking at overall mean score and the mean score for each item. This had provided a full reading of the results and a tool to check the validity. We chose to show the means in figures to provide a better reading to indicate "Weak", "Average", "Moderate", "Good", or "Excellent" results as in Table 4.

Table 4

Mean Indicator

Weak	Average	Moderate	Good	Excellent
< 2.5	[2.5-3]	[3-3.5]	[3.5-4]	>4

The results were sorted out in different tables in order to examine averages, means percentages, and get standard deviation. Validity, Reliability, and tests for Significance were run systematically. To measure the internal consistency of the four

domains of the questionnaire, we also used SPSS to compute Cronbach's Alpha (see Table 3).

As for the interviews and the open-ended question of the SSS, the answers were coded into quantitative responses (Appendix C) for analysis. This qualitative data was handled in the following way: data of responses were collected, then coded and grouped for homogeneity, and then the frequency of responses were quantified and then analyzed in order to get a clear quantitative insight into the suggestions, complaints, or information students had given.

Ethical Consideration

The research conducted involved students from grade 7 till 12 of the Evangelical Heritage School (EHS), a pseudonym replacing the actual name of the actual school due to the sensitive information and internal reports used. Participating students were encouraged to answer all questions as this would reflect their "voice" about the school. Also, this would help the administration to improve the school performance. They were given the freedom to answer up to their knowledge, anonymously, without any pressure or interference. Besides that, students were given the space to write their opinion under "Remark" section leaving that up to them whether they want to express their feelings on any aspect unnoticed in the survey or not. Likewise, students interviewed were in a relaxing atmosphere and were able to express their feelings freely.

All information obtained was sorted out professionally as to receive clear and transparent data to reflect reality. All measures concerning validity and reliability of the instrument used, correlation, regression, and cross-tabulation of data were conducted to reach the true results.

CHAPTER 4

DATA ANALYSIS

In this chapter, we will analyze the data to address the research questions and find the reasons why students intend to leave EHS. Firstly, we will consider the *Demographics* part of the survey and focus on what the data showed in order to link it with other data observations. The demographic part of the survey has 11 questions, however, question number 11 “I’m leaving EHS to another school” will be treated separately as dependent variable. Next, we will run the Correlation and Reliability Test on the *Four Domains* of the SSS as we analyze the 30 questions one by one. Also, question number 30 “I’m satisfied with my experience at EHS” will be treated separately as dependent variable. Following that, we will deal with the qualitative responses that represent the students’ feedback in the *Remarks* section of the SSS and the summary of the *Interviews*. Finally, we will manipulate the data in different ways using Regression, Cross-Tabulation, and Correlation tests to find out what is making students want to leave EHS.

Demographics of the Study

More male than female students participated in this survey as shown in Table 5, with males being 59% as compared to 41% females.

Table 5

Gender Representation and Number of Participants

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent
Valid	Female	71	41.5	41.5
	Male	100	58.5	58.5
	Total	171	100	100.0

The highest participation rate for this study was amongst students in Grades 10 and 11 at 21% each, while the lowest was found in grade 9 at 11% in addition to Grade 12 which scored 12% as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Student participation according to class.

The analysis of the demographics of the survey showed that a majority of 92% of the students mentioned living with their parents, with very few of them living with their mother only (6%), with their father only (2%), or with their grandparents (1%).

On the other hand, when asking the students about the education level of their parents, 68% stated that their father had university degree, while 28% mentioned that their father had a high school degree and only 4% of the fathers had no education at all. Although a university degree was also seen the highest among student's mothers as well, yet it was lower than that of the fathers registering 62%. Unlike the fathers with a high school diploma, mothers with the same degree constituted 36%, and only 2% with no education at all as shown in Table 6.

Table 6

Parents' Educational Level

	Parents' Education	Fathers' Education			Mothers' education		
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent
Valid	No education	6	3.5	3.8	4	2.3	2.5
	High school	45	26.3	28.5	57	33.3	35.6
	University Degree	107	62.6	67.7	99	57.9	61.9
	Total	158	92.4	100.0	160	93.6	100.0
Missing	System	13	7.6		11	6.4	
	Total	171	100.0		171	100.0	

As for the one providing a living to students, 48% declared that their fathers were the only ones working in the household, in addition to another 47% who had both of their parents working, while only 5% mentioned that their mothers were the

only person who was working nowadays. The percentages of parents actually working show a significant discrepancy between males and females having a university degree. We notice that almost 68% of the fathers hold a university degree compared to 62% of mothers. This difference may be attributed to the fact that 90% of our students came from Muslim background where mothers stay at home to take care of the big family. Most of the time when parents were invited to attend a lecture, meet with teachers for academic feedback, or receive orientation about the school’s vision, objectives, and activities, the attendees were mostly women with very few men.

Students answering about their family income according to their knowledge was indicated in Table 7, where 36% of the students mentioned that their family income ranged between 500 and 2,000 USD, followed directly by 34% who had higher family income between 2,001 and 5,000 USD. Whilst 15% of the sample stated their household earned even more than 5,000 USD. Yet, 26 students or 15.2% did not give any answer, as not all students know their parents’ income. We can only treat the answers to this question as informed estimations since we cannot fully verify how many students accurately know their parents’ income.

Table 7

Parents’ Yearly Income

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent
Valid	500-2000 USD	61	35.7	42.1
	2001-5000 USD	59	34.5	40.7
	5000+ USD	25	14.6	17.2
	Total	145	84.8	100.0
Missing	System	26	15.2	
Total		171	100.0	

Furthermore, when students were asked about the means of transportation that they used to commute to school, different ways were used with the highest being by school bus at 40%, followed by their parents 35%, while the remaining 25% stated coming by private minivans or even taxis. This indicated that 60% of parents were not using the school bus. This result came to show that the tuition fees ranging from LL 5,200,000 - at KGs till LL 7,300,000 - at the secondary level in addition to the bus fees ranging from LL 800,000.- till 1,300,000.- were a heavy load on parents with such salaries (Principal's Report, 2019).

Table 8 below indicates the number of students enrolled at a certain grade. It shows at a certain grade how many students started from preschool, elementary, intermediate, or secondary level. So in Grade 12, 17 students had joined the school at preschool and 3 at the elementary level while no one joined at the intermediate or secondary level. It is remarkable that, out of 171 students surveyed, 125 students had started school from preschool level, 27 from elementary level, 14 from intermediate level, and 5 joined the secondary level. This shows a good number of students who started school from preschool level who we assume were satisfied with EHS. There were 5 new students (3 at Grade 10 and 2 at Grade 11) joining EHS at the secondary level.

To elaborate more, it is remarkable that 73% of the students, as indicated in Figure 3 below, showed their loyalty to EHS, since they had been registered in it from the preschool level, for a total of 67 students who were now in Grades 10, 11, and 12. This number represents 54% of the 125 who continued from preschool into secondary level. Moreover, EHS managed to attract new students as well but at a much lesser rate, with 3% who mentioned starting their education at EHS from the secondary level. On the other hand, 16% of the students, mentioned were enrolled at

EHS from the elementary level and 8%, from the intermediate level. Students usually do not change schools at the secondary level except for extreme cases because of the risk of not being accepted in other schools or because they are used to the style of their school.

Table 8

Class and Level of Starting School

Starting Education	Class						Total
	Grade 7	Grade 8	Grade 9	Grade 10	Grade 11	Grade 12	
Preschool	20	26	12	25	25	17	125
Elementary	8	2	4	5	5	3	27
Intermediate	1	5	2	2	4	0	14
Secondary	0	0	0	3	2	0	5
Total	29	33	18	35	36	20	171

Figure 3. When students joined the school.

Students were asked about their grades and where do they rank in their class. One fourth of the sample, as shown in Figure 4, said that they had scored between 86 and 100 which put them among the high achieving list at EHS. However, the next two rank brackets with much higher student percentages were the 76-85 bracket with a 40% and the 61-75 bracket at 32%. During 2017-2018 and 2018-2019 academic years, 50% of Elementary students and 40% of Intermediate Secondary students were on the Honor List (Principal's Report, 2019).

Figure 4. Students' grading and rank in class.

These were the data analysis of the demographic questions of the first part of the SSS survey which was designed to measure the school climate and student intention to leave the school trying to find out what is causing student to think of dropping out or leaving to another school. Next, we will analyze the four domains of school climate item by item to find any item that indicates why students might intend to leave the school.

The Four Domains of School Climate

The SSS is divided into four domains as follows:

1. Personal/Social Environment
2. Physical Environment
3. Learning/Cognitive Environment
4. Moral Environment

Figure 5 shows the means of each of the four domains separately. Upon comparing the means, it was noticed that the Personal/Social environment topped the list since it registered the highest agreement amongst all of the students scoring a mean of 3.605. In second place came Moral Environment at 3.547 with a slight difference from the Learning/Cognitive Environment that came in the third place at 3.537. While the lowest domain mean was given for the Physical Environment scoring 3.037, which arose from the dissatisfaction from the classroom, playground, library and laboratories found in the EHS as it will be discussed later on.

Figure 5. Mean results for each domain of SSS.

Four Domains Correlation Test

In this section we aim to give a general view of the correlation between the domains and then take each domain to analyze it within its items. When each domain is analyzed by looking at overall mean score, we will take every question in that domain in detail and check the mean score for each item which represents the mean score of the students' responses. To make it more vivid, we added the Mean Indicator to show the range of "Weak", "Average", "Moderate", "Good", or "Excellent" results as shown in Table 9.

Table 9

Mean Indicator

Weak	Average	Moderate	Good	Excellent
< 2.5	[2.5-3]	[3-3.5]	[3.5-4]	> 4

After performing the correlation between the four domains, it was seen that there was a statistically significant correlation between our variables since the Sig (2-tailed) value was less than 0.05, as shown in Table 10.

Furthermore, after examining the Pearson correlation, it was noticed that there was a relationship between all of the four domains in general, where the strongest relationship was between Personal/Social and Moral environment having $r = 0.732$, while the weakest was between Personal/Social and Physical environment with $r = 0.473$. In the following sections, we will elaborate on the meaning of these correlations.

Table 10

Correlations of the Four Domains of School Climate

		AVG Personal/ Social	AVG Physical	AVG learning/ Cognitive	AVG Moral
AVG Personal/ Social	Pearson Correlation	1	.473**	.595**	.732**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000
	N	171	171	171	171
AVG Physical	Pearson Correlation	.473**	1	.567**	.560**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000
	N	171	171	171	171
AVG Learn/ Cognitive	Pearson Correlation	.595**	.567**	1	.531**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000
	N	171	171	171	171
AVG Moral	Pearson Correlation	.732**	.560**	.531**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	
	N	171	171	171	171

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Personal/Social Environment

When examining each domain along with its group of items, it was seen that the Personal/Social environment scored the highest mean across all (3.605). This resulted mainly because of the two items “*Parents are proud with the official exam results*” and “*The good relationship found with the teachers,*” since both registered an excellent mean reaching 4.17 and 4.06 respectively. Moreover, almost all the rest

of the items registered good mean values that affected the overall total mean, where the highest was seen for “*EHS having a good reputation in the community*” at 3.9, followed by “*Having open, honest and active communication between teachers and students and between teachers and parents as well*” at 3.81. On the other hand, as shown in Figure 6, only one item dealing with “*Enrolling children at EHS in the future*” had an average mean of 2.74 which was the lowest amongst all of the Personal/Social environment items.

Figure 6. Personal/Social Environment means.

At this point, we will analyze the students' feedback on the first domain, which was the Personal/Social domain, and it consisted of 8 questions. For the first question, Figure 7 shows that 59% of the students agreed that they felt EHS was their home out of which only 16% strongly agreed with the statement. On the other hand, 20% of the sample, expressed their disagreement and strong disagreement with the statement.

Figure 7. Responses to Personal/Social question “I feel EHS is my home.”

More than half (53%) of the students agreed that they were treated as an individual. In addition, another 8% expressed their strong agreement (Figure 8), thus reaching a total of 61% of who agree. On the other hand, 19% were not satisfied with the way they were treated in school. Also, 20% were neutral, showing reluctance in expressing their feelings.

Figure 8. Responses to Personal/Social question “I’m treated as an individual.”

When students were asked about their relationship with their teachers, a high proportion of 82% of students agreed that they were in a good relationship with their teachers, where more than one fourth of them strongly agreed with this statement. This resulted in a small number who expressed a poor relationship with their teachers; disagreement and strong disagreement totaled 5% of the sample, as in Figure 9.

Figure 9. Responses to Personal/Social question “I’m in good relationship with my teachers.”

However, when we compared this result with what 111 out of 171 students wrote in the remark section in the survey, the qualitative part, we found a completely different response which showed the highest negative remarks focusing on the problem of teachers' behavior: teachers don't treat everyone equally, and even recommend changing some teachers. So, we got 28 negative remarks focusing on teachers amounting for 25% of the 111 students who gave the remarks. The most likely explanation was that students were in good relationship with their teachers although they didn't like their teachers' attitude. Also, Figure 8 showed that 19% of students did not feel they were treated as individuals, probably signaling dissatisfaction with their teachers because they felt they were uncaring and unsupportive.

In answering a question about "open, honest and active communication occurs between teachers-students, and teachers-parents," 71% of students, as shown in Figure 10, described the communication between them and the teachers and even between teachers and parents as being open, honest and active; unlike 9% who were not satisfied with the way the communication occurred. Also, we notice that 20.5% of students chose not to give their feedback, and this might be because they didn't see that their teachers exhibit "open, honest, and active communication" or they didn't see any "open, honest, and active communication" between teachers and parents. Also, if we combine their responses with Disagree and Strongly Disagree responses, we get about 30% of total students who were not satisfied with their teachers.

Figure 10. Responses to Personal/Social question “open, honest and active communication occurs between teachers-students, and teachers-parents.”

Out of the total sample, it was seen that 18% of them disagreed that their families considered EHS warm, inviting and helpful, as compared to more than two thirds (67%) who agreed, as shown in Figure 11.

Figure 11. Responses to Personal/Social question “my family considers EHS warm, inviting and helpful.”

Regarding the results of EHS in the official exams, as shown in Figure 12, we noticed that 37% of the students strongly expressed their parents' pride, in addition to 45% who agreed with them as well, thus resulting with a total agreement of 82%. However, fewer than 8% expressed their disagreement with the above.

Figure 12. Responses to Personal/Social question “my parents are proud of EHS results in the official exams.”

The above responses confirmed the good results our students had achieved over the years. For example, in 2018, EHS students got the rank of 3rd and 9th in Beirut district in Life Sciences, 3rd in Beirut district in General Sciences, and 25th over Lebanon in Economics (Principal’s Report, 2018). Also in 2019, one of our diligent students ranked 9th in Beirut district in G9 2018-2019 Official exams. The school always felt proud of the students’ outstanding academic performance. The percentage of students with an honor mention of Good and Very Good in the Official Exams 2018-2019 came to be 65% G12 and 78% G9 (Principal’s Report, 2019).

When asked about the good reputation that EHS has in the community, 74% students declared their agreement as compared to disagreement of 7%. Furthermore, as shown in Figure 13, 19% of the sample had a neutral opinion on their school reputation indirectly expressing their own, their peers, or their parents' dissatisfaction.

Figure 13. Responses to Personal/Social question “EHS has good reputation in the community.”

The final response regarding the Personal/Social Environment asking about future enrollment of the students' children at EHS, had much different scores than all the rest of the domains as in Figure 14. Whereas, the highest percentage was amongst students with a neutral opinion at 39%, followed by those who disagreed with this specific domain at 40%, we see a surprising low 21% only who agreed to enroll their children at EHS in the future.

So, here these questions are asked: if students are happy with their school would they leave? In the future would they want to enroll their own kids in the same school? This study aims to find the answers. We will give this item more attention later on as we manipulate the data to find out the reasons.

Figure 14. Responses to Personal/Social question “in the future, I will enroll my children at EHS.”

Physical Environment

As for the second domain, which was the Physical Environment, it registered the lowest total mean among all of the four domains. This was due to having the majority of its items scoring moderate average and even lower.

What is worth mentioning in this Physical environment is that only two of its items resulted with a good mean which were “*Students feel safe everywhere on EHS property*” and “*Rules regarding safety and expected behavior*” at 3.87 and 3.65 respectively as shown in Figure 15. While “*Canteens providing what is needed*” and “*Having classrooms and grounds clean and well maintained*” scored moderate mean of 3.42 and 3.46. Moreover, three of the items had an average mean between 2.5 and 3, where students were asked about their satisfaction with the “*Labs*”, “*Playgrounds*” and “*Classrooms rich with works created by the students*”.

In addition to the above low averages, one item scored a significantly weak average of 1.9 reflecting the dissatisfaction with the Library.

The first question of this domain, as in Figure 16, the students’ answers indicated that 61% of the sample were satisfied with the cleanliness and maintenance

of classrooms and grounds found at school, while 22% disagreed with the situation, with another 18% who expressed a neutral opinion about this matter.

Figure 15. Physical Environment means.

Figure 16. Responses to Physical question “classrooms and grounds are clean and well-maintained.”

Less satisfaction was seen towards the Physical Environment, as shown in Figure 17, especially when talking about school and classrooms being rich with displays of works created by students. However, 37% of the students disagreed and strongly disagreed with the statement and another 28% expressed a neutral opinion, while 35% declared their agreement with the above. We realize that this could be a significantly serious problem.

Figure 17. Responses to Physical question “school and classrooms are rich with displays of works created by students.”

As for the library at EHS, we noted a major problem that should be addressed, since there were 41% students who were strongly dissatisfied with it in addition to 33% who disagreed thus resulting in a total of nearly three fourths of the sample. On the other hand, as shown in Figure 18, only 8% agreed that the library resources were adequate and useful while only 1% who strongly agree with it.

Figure 18. Responses to Physical question “I’m satisfied with EHS library.”

The responses above reflected the truth and this was due to the fact that EHS lived through different war situations where it had to change location as described in the introduction. The current campus is a small campus and due to the need of space the Library was replaced by the Special Education Department. Most of the books were compiled in boxes and students had no access to the library anymore. Still yet unsatisfactory, students have book-shelves in each class and have stories to read but without the physical Library.

Students’ feelings towards the library overlaps with their feeling towards the playground where half of them were dissatisfied with EHS playground out of which 19% were strongly disagreed. On the other hand, 32% agreed, out of which only 4% expressed their extreme satisfaction with their playgrounds as shown in Figure 19. There was only one playground at EHS for Grades 7-12 students; uncovered, unpainted, and also used for buses during dismissal. Usually, the school rents a nearby professional covered basketball and green football playgrounds for sports events and competitions. Students compare the professional playground with their school playground and that is why 67.6% came *Neutral* to *Totally Disagree*.

Figure 19. Responses to Physical question “I’m satisfied with EHS playground.”

Similarly more dissatisfaction was seen when talking about EHS labs, where 32% mentioned their strong disagreement with it, and another 23% mentioned their disagreement which resulted in a total of 55% dissatisfaction. On the other hand, 31% of the sample were satisfied with only 5% of them being extremely satisfied. EHS has a small lab that contains all the basic experiments needed to support instructions. More and more teachers are moving towards the Virtual Lab in classes. Technology tools have their own value and are becoming a must, but they should not replace the traditional laboratories (Scheckler, 2003). Scheckler (2003) argued that even though interactive computers provide simulation, yet students feel hands-on labs provide a very special type of learning engagement. Students in traditional lab activities are engaged physically, emotionally, as well as mentally. Even though students are becoming more digitized, they still love the empirical way of learning as expressed in Figure 20.

Figure 20. Responses to Physical question “I’m satisfied with EHS labs.”

As for the canteen, Figure 21, it came better than the rest of EHS Physical environment since more than half (57%) agreed that it provides what they need. On the other hand, 21% disagreed expressing that the canteen does not provide them with what they need.

Figure 21. Responses to physical question “the canteen provides what I need.”

The canteen at EHS went into major renovations at the beginning of the summer of 2018 and was transformed from a small Canteen into a Cafeteria that catered different types of sandwiches, burgers, and healthy food (Principal' Report, 2019). Since then students could no longer buy junk food and unhealthy stuff, most likely resulting in the 8.3% Strongly Disagree.

Out of the total sample, as shown in Figure 22, three fourths of them (75%) mentioned feeling safe everywhere on EHS property, including 23% strongly agreeing with that. In comparison, 14% disagreed with the situation including only 5% stating their strong disagreement.

Figure 22. Responses to Physical question “Students feel safe everywhere on EHS property.”

In the final question of the Physical Environment, 51% of the students agreed with EHS rules and regulations regarding safety and expected behavior being clear in addition to 18% who strongly agreed as well. Furthermore, as shown in Figure 23, fewer disagreements were seen where 9% expressed their disagreement with the rules and regulations along with 8% being strongly disagreed as well.

Figure 23. Responses to Physical question “EHS rules and regulations regarding safety and expected behavior are clear.”

The Learning/Cognitive Environment

The third domain was the Learning/Cognitive Environment and it consisted of 9 questions. Almost all of the items found under the Learning/Cognitive environment scored a good average with the highest seen for “*Students are assigned to research, prepare presentations and present in class*” at 3.97. In second place is “*EHS educational level is very high*” at 3.93, as shown in Figure 24.

The two lowest items were “Satisfaction with afterschool activities” with a mean of 2.15, and “Progress is monitored, evaluated regularly and shared with parents” with a moderate mean of 3.44.

For the first question in this domain, as shown in Figure 25, 57% of the students declared their agreement on being encouraged to succeed through the support and efforts of teachers and administration. Of these, 16% of them strongly agreed with the encouragement received. In contrast, a total of 12% stated their disagreement with the way they were encouraged and supported to succeed.

Figure 24. Learning/Cognitive Environment means.

Figure 25. Responses to Learning/Cognitive question “Students are encouraged to succeed.”

Regarding question number 18 about academic expectations being high for all students, the highest percentage was seen amongst students who agreed (46%), in addition to 15% stating they strongly agreed. However, 18% of the students were

neutral and 17% disagreed. In the current academic year 2019-2020, and in spite of all the disturbance and pressure on students due to the protests in the country, 23% of Elementary students and 31% of Intermediate and Secondary students were on the Honor List (Principal's Report, 2019 This showed that the administration and teachers had high expectations for all students to excel in their academics.

Moreover, when asked about educational of the school, as shown in Figure 26, 75% of the students agreed and strongly agreed that EHS's educational level is high.

Figure 26. Responses to Learning/Cognitive question “EHS educational level is very high.”

In response to question number 20 (Figure 27), “Achievements and performance are rewarded, praised and publicly displayed”, 55% of the sample, agreed that their achievements and performance were rewarded; besides, 18% strongly agreed that they were rewarded and publicly praised. Conversely, 14% were neutral and 12% disagreed in general.

Figure 27. Responses to Learning/Cognitive question “achievements and performance are rewarded, praised and publicly displayed.”

Also, Figure 28 showed that the majority of the students (85%), agreed and strongly agreed that EHS stressed on students to give their best by assigning them research, preparation of presentations, and presentations in class. There was only an 8% who disagreed with the idea.

Figure 28. Responses to Learning/Cognitive question “students are assigned to research, prepare a presentation, and present in class.”

In Figure 29, different opinions were given by the students regarding how progress is monitored, evaluated regularly, and even shared with the parents, where 48% of them expressed their agreement and 19% who disagreed with the idea. However, the lowest percentages were amongst those who strongly agreed and even strongly disagreed at 9% and 2% respectively.

Figure 29. Responses to Learning/Cognitive question “progress is monitored, evaluated regularly, and shared with parents.”

In general, students at EHS are followed up individually and there are three main meetings per year with parents and teachers to discuss each student’s progress besides other occasions depending on the performance of the student. That explains why 61% of the total sample, as shown previously in Figure 8, stated that they were treated as an individual.

On the other hand, Figure 30 shows higher dissatisfaction among students when responding about afterschool activities, where 37% expressed their strong dissatisfaction in addition to 26% who were dissatisfied thus resulting in a total of

63% with disagreement. Moreover, 21% of the sample had neutral opinion and 15% were the only satisfied students with the way the school was handling such activities.

Figure 30. Responses to Learning/Cognitive question “I’m satisfied with afterschool activities.”

The school initiated Sports, Drama, Zumba, and Taekwondo clubs in the academic year 2016-2017, and it was a successful experience. However, students still preferred to subscribe in the nearby clubs and at other professional playgrounds. There were still few extracurricular activities such as a Music Club teaching violin and guitar, Arts Club, and Football Club for elementary level.

What was obvious in Figure 31 was that students were not satisfied with their teachers’ behavior, since only 16% agreed with the item “Teachers are caring and supportive” as compared to 33% who disagreed with it. However, more than half 51% refused to give their sincere opinion and rather showed their neutral attitude towards their teachers in general. The issue of students’ dissatisfaction with their teachers was more and more coming up to the surface.

Figure 31. Responses to Learning/Cognitive question “teachers are caring and supportive.”

As for whether classroom size and ratio of students-to-teacher were helpful to learning or not, 68% of the students agreed while only 14% disagreed. In fact, there were two sections in each class except for Grades 9, 11, and 12. The largest number of students was 36 in Grade 11. In General Sciences (GS) and Sociology and Economics (SE) there were only 5 students as shown in Table 11. The ratio of teacher to students is 1 to 9 in the secondary level (Principal’s Report, 2018). This ratio is the most important factor that increases students’ achievement and success as the interaction between teachers and students becomes more effective (Koc & Celik, 2015). Students in some classes like GS, LS, and SE are as if they were taking private lessons when it comes to the number of students in each class.

Moral Environment

The fourth domain is the Moral Environment and it consisted of 5 questions. Regarding the Moral environment, as classified in the Mean Indicator, Figure 32 showed that only one item had a Moderate mean of 3.44 talking about “*the educational EHS program include development of knowledge and skills that promote ethical decision making and conflict resolution.*” The rest of the items registered Good means varying between 3.52 and 3.79.

Table 11

Students in Cycle 3 and Secondary

EHS Number of Students per Cycle per Class			
Cycle 3	Number of Students	Secondary	Number of Students
G9 A	18	GS	5
G9 B	0	LS	10
G8 A	17	SE	5
G8 B	16	G11	36
G7 A	15	G10 A	18
G7 B	14	G10 B	17
Total	80	Total	91
No. of Teachers	12	No. of Teachers (Full Timers)	10
Ratio	1 teacher to 6.6 students		1 teacher to 9.1 students

Figure 32. Moral environment means.

or the first question in this domain, as shown in Figure 33, the majority of students 75% agreed that EHS valued diversity out of which 15% strongly agreed. Moreover, 13% were neutral towards their school values in addition to another 12% who disagreed with that.

To add to that, students at EHS come from different backgrounds, with the majority being non-Christians, even so for teachers, and yet all feel welcome under EHS mission statement. That is why, 59% of the students agreed that they felt EHS as their home, and 16% strongly agreed with the statement as we have seen previously in the first question “I feel EHS is my Home” in Personal/Social Environment.

Figure 33. Responses to Moral question “EHS values diversity and is welcoming to all cultures.”

Also as Figure 34 indicates, agreeing with the way EHS built the students’ character, responses came to be 14% strongly agree while the highest registering 43% is for agree, followed by 24% who had a neutral opinion and 16% who disagreed with this issue. Moreover, students who declared their strong disagreement scored the lowest percentages at 4%.

Figure 34. Responses to Moral question “EHS has built my character with values and respect.”

Throughout the elementary cycles, students have one Ethics hour per week in which they learn the Christian values on which the school Mission Statement is based. There are other programs for Intermediate and Secondary levels such as: Leaders for Lebanon, Character Assessment Program, and awareness lectures given to students in collaboration with Wazanat, a well-known institution for Career Counseling and Professional Orientation in Lebanon (Principal’s Report, 2018).

When talking about staff, students, and families and how they demonstrated school pride, 58% mentioned their agreement as compared to only 11% who mentioned their disagreement with this issue as indicated in Figure 35. Parents were proud that their kids were students at EHS. This pride was built on the good reputation EHS had gained over many years and on its good results on the national level.

Figure 35. Responses to Moral question “staff, students, and families demonstrate school pride.”

As Figure 36 indicates, 56% of the students agreed and strongly agreed with their schools educational program, especially how it included skills development that promoted ethical decision making along with conflict resolution. Furthermore, 23% were neutral and 21% of the students disagreed with the above. EHS teachers have been trained on a holistic curriculum over a three-day period called “Dream-Makers or Dream-Breakers” based on empowering students to make right decisions when they encounter life diverging choices. Separate programs were given to Grades 7 and 8 on *Presentation skills*, *Time management*, and *Conflict Resolution* which will cultivate students’ characters.

Figure 36. Responses to Moral question “EHS and its educational program include development of knowledge/skills that promote ethical decision-making and conflict resolution.”

Again here, we will use the Mean Indicator, as in Table 12, which indicates the range of means with different colors for *Weak*, *Average*, *Moderate*, *Good*, or *Excellent*.

Table 12

Mean Indicator

Weak	Average	Moderate	Good	Excellent
< 2.5	[2.5-3]	[3-3.5]	[3.5-4]	>4

We have analyzed the students’ responses to SSS in details. In Table 13 we will see the summary of SSS responses focusing on the mean.

Table 13

Summary Item Statistics of SSS

Summary Item Statistics	Mean
P1. I feel EHS is my home	3.53
P2. I'm treated as an individual	3.51
P3. I'm in good relationship with my teachers	4.06
P4. Open, honest and active communication occurs between teachers-students, and teachers-parents	3.81
P5. My family considers EHS warm, inviting and helpful	3.62
P6. My parents are proud of EHS results in the official exams	4.17
P7. EHS has good reputation in the community	3.90
P8. In the future, I will enroll my children at EHS	2.74
PH9. Classrooms and grounds are clean and well-maintained	3.46
PH10. School and classrooms are rich with displays of works created by students	2.94
PH11. I'm satisfied with EHS library	1.90
PH12. I'm satisfied with EHS playground	2.67
PH13. I'm satisfied with EHS labs	2.53
PH14. The canteen provides what I need	3.42
PH15. Students feel safe everywhere on EHS property	3.87
PH16. EHS rules and regulations regarding safety and expected behavior are clear	3.65
L17. Students are encouraged to succeed	3.80
L18. Expectations are high for all students	3.60
L19. EHS educational level is very high	3.93
L20. Achievements and performance are rewarded, praised and publicly displayed	3.72
L21. Students are assigned to research, prepare a presentation, and present in class	3.97
L22. Progress is monitored, evaluated regularly, and shared with parents	3.44
L23. I'm satisfied with afterschool activities	2.15
L24. Teachers are caring and supportive	3.73
L25. Classroom size and ratio of students-to-teacher are helpful to learning	3.72
M26. EHS values diversity and is welcoming to all cultures	3.79
M27. EHS has built my character with values and respect	3.52
M28. Staff, students, and families demonstrate school pride	3.55
M29. EHS and its educational program include development of knowledge/ skills that promote ethical decision-making and conflict resolution	3.44
M30. I'm satisfied with my experience at EHS	3.72

The top 5 means, as Table 14 shows, were all related to the Personal/Social and Learning/Cognitive Environments, which was a rather important indicator that the educational system in the school and the Personal domain have raised the total mean to a higher level.

Table 14

The Top 5 Most Influential Positive Questions

P6.	My parents are proud of EHS results in the official exams	4.17
L21.	Students are assigned to research, prepare a presentation, and present in class	3.97
L19.	EHS educational level is very high	3.93
P7.	EHS has good reputation in the community	3.90
L17.	Students are encouraged to succeed	3.80

Below, in Table 15, we see the questions with the 5 lowest means, three being Physical revealing the impact of the premise, such as library, labs, and playground on the students' responses, with one Learning/Cognitive Environment, and one Personal/Social Environment. It was clearly shown that the problem was in the facilities and amenities, which lowered the good averages the school had, especially when asking about activities. Another matter of concern surfaces when asking about the future of student enrollment at EHS. The mean of 2.74 rings an alarm as to the future continuity and stability of the school since our current students are not strongly convinced of having their children at EHS.

Table 15

Most Negative Answers

PH11.I'm satisfied with EHS library	1.90
L23.I'm satisfied with afterschool activities	2.15
PH13.I'm satisfied with EHS labs	2.53
PH12.I'm satisfied with EHS playground	2.67
P8.In the future, I will enroll my children at EHS	2.74

Student Satisfaction

Finally, when asking students about their satisfaction with their EHS experience nearly half 46% declared their agreement, followed by those who were neutral and even strongly agreed at 21% and 20% respectively. While only few disagreed at 7% and another 6% who declared their strong disagreement with their experience as shown in Figure 37.

Figure 37. Responses to Moral question "I'm satisfied with my experience at EHS."

However, we will separately use this question, “I’m satisfied with my experience at EHS” in Moral Environment, as an independent variable to other items in the survey.

Intention to Leave

Students were asked about their future at EHS, whether they want to continue till they graduate, leave to another school or travel. The responses are presented in percentages in Figure 38. Different opinions were given by students regarding their future intentions towards the school; with 78% of them expressing their willingness to continue until graduation being the highest and main intention. In second place came the group of students who were graduating the same year at 13%. Others expressed their intentions of either leaving to another school at 6% or travelling at 3.6%. The 6% represents 10 students in the total sample. Further analysis of these percentages will be given through this chapter. We will use this question as dependent variable to measure “students leaving EHS” later in our analysis.

Figure 38. Students’ feedback about their future education at EHS.

Analysis of Qualitative Responses

As mentioned previously, the students were given the chance to voice their opinions about issues the SSS might have missed or unintentionally ignored. The responses were categorized in order to derive some statistics. The qualitative results consisted of two parts. The first part was the answers collected through the SSS, and the second part was the 10 interviews with students.

Summary of Qualitative Section in SSS

In the last section of the SSS, students had the chance to write open-endedly in the Remark section. 111 students wrote down 152 remarks on different aspects of school climate. That meant out of the total sample, 65% of the students wrote down their remarks about EHS, which varied between positive, moderate and negative feedback about the school (Table 16).

Table 17 shows the responses re-arranged by frequency and percentages. It shows, in blue color, that the highest individual yet lowest overall percentage was noted for the positive feedback scoring 20% where students stated loving their school and that it was the best school, However, the lowest percentage registered was for the negative feedback, scoring 62% aggregated.

The top main reason for negative feedback were their teachers' behavior (13%); changing some rules and systems came second at 11%, like allowing students to wear some accessories with the uniform, wear random shoes, haircut, etc.; and thirdly was that teachers didn't treat students equally at 9%, suggesting that teachers were biased toward some students. Other reasons were also mentioned but at lesser percentages such as changing some teachers and expensive fees at 5% each; improve restrooms by adding soap, tissues and AC to absorb the smell, have less homework and stress of exams, and the administration not to bias towards some teachers at 4%

each. As for the moderate feedback, it was mentioned by 55% of the students and ranged between 4% and 15%.

Table 16

Number of Remarks in the Qualitative Section of the SSS

Remarks (n=111 students)	Total Frequency	Percentage	Positive Negative Moderate
Best school	22	19.82%	P
Need more activities	17	15.32%	M
Sole problem is some teachers' behavior	14	12.61%	N
Put AC in all classes	12	10.81%	M
Must change some rules and systems	11	9.91%	N
Don't treat everyone equally	9	8.11%	N
Some days must be given to reading/better library	7	6.31%	M
Better playground/ pay attention to sports hours	6	5.41%	M
Change some teachers	5	4.50%	N
Fees are high/expensive	5	4.50%	N
Awareness over mental health is needed	4	3.60%	M
Have more variety foods in canteen	4	3.60%	M
Focus on the artistic side	4	3.60%	M
Restrooms need to be better	4	3.60%	N
Less homework	4	3.60%	N
Less stress of exams	4	3.60%	N
School is sometimes bias toward some teachers	4	3.60%	N
School needs technological development	3	2.70%	N
Better laboratory	3	2.70%	N
Make this school great again	2	1.80%	M
Some children are bullied by bigger students	2	1.80%	N
Make school more fun	1	0.90%	M
Should break free of Lebanese chains	1	0.90%	M
Should support certain online learning platform	1	0.90%	M
Give us choice for not participating in PE class	1	0.90%	M
I really hate my bus driver	1	0.90%	N
Lower period time from 50 to 45 minutes	1	0.90%	M

Table 17

Totals of the Positive, Negative, and Moderate Feedback

Grouping	Total Frequency	Percentage
Negative Feedback (N)	69	62.13%
Moderate Feedback (M)	61	54.95%
Positive Feedback (P)	22	19.82%

So, if we take the negative remarks and regroup again, we get 28 negative remarks out of 125 responses focusing on teachers amounting to 18.42 of the total remarks or 25% out of the number of 111 students who gave the remarks.

Summary of the Interviews

We interviewed 10 students selected randomly, two from each Grades 7, 8, 9, 10, and 11; five males and five females. Students were asked 10 questions listed in Appendix B, and they were encouraged to express their feelings and any concerns as we can see with the summary of their answers in Appendix C.

Students interviewed expressed themselves freely and from different perspectives. In answering about their definition of a good school and whether they see their school like that. Most responses came to be positive. For example, Hanine, a Grade 7 student, replied that “a good school is where there is good teacher-student relationships and the students are able to understand the subjects being taught to them from teachers who have experience in teaching. My school is with high standards of education and has a very comfortable atmosphere.” However, 22% of the responses such as Bilal, a Grade 8 student, said that “a good school cultivates individuals with good social skills and not just education.” Most of the responses like Nader, Grade 9 student came to say that: “a good school has a high standard of education, restricts

bullying and controls anything that causes discomfort to students. My school is safe and welcoming.” Sara defined a good school saying: “A school with good education and teaches its students to be better people, and I like everything about this school.”

There were different replies to the question about the school rules and regulations. More than 60% of the responses like the response of Nizar, a Grade 7 student, and Aya, grade 10 student, expressed that “they are strict and unfair, not flexible, and not logical, while other schools are more lenient.” Sara and others (22%) felt that: “They are made for our good.” As for Nader “if the student is not serious about education, the rules would seem strict. But if the student is attending school to learn and be serious, the rules are fair and just right.”

When participants were asked about one thing they would like to change in their school, Hanine and others, representing 25% of the responses, said that: “The school should be more mindful when scheduling tests and exams.” Bilal, a Grade 8 student, as well as Aya replied that the one thing they liked to see changed is: “The curriculum. The school has to concentrate a bit more on creativity rather than on books and finishing the curriculum. This school should be more unique.” Amani, a Grade 9 student said, “I ask for equality; some teachers play favoritism and do not even look at other students.”

About continuing at EHS or if they were given the chance to leave to another school, would they go and what would be the reason? Most responses, amounting to 93%, responded with “No.” Hanine, Nizar, Bilal, Yasmine, Amani, Nader, Adam, and Sara said that: “No, because I believe that this is the best school around,” “No, I wouldn’t go because I have everything in this school. Everything is related to me,” and “No, because I believe that this is the best school around.” Aya was the only response saying: “Yes, because most schools concentrate more on activities and have

less pressure; less studying.” However, Jad, a Grade 10 student, said that: “of course not; it would feel like leaving my family.”

The answers to every question were in qualitative form. They were listed then classified or grouped under topics in order to count the frequency of similar responses and the percentages in order to be able to read and analyze the responses. For example, in Table 18, the ten students gave different answers during the interview to the question how they define a good school. The answers were classified according into topics and finally we got eight groups of answers. The frequency represents the number of the same or similar answers to each question and not the number of students. We will comment on particular items that represent the answers with the highest percentage.

As shown in Table 18, in the answer to define a good school and describe its atmosphere, students expressed that their school provided a safe and comfortable environment. However, some responses described the school rules and regulations to be strict, unfair, and not flexible. Students expressed that the challenges they faced were getting good grades, maintaining high grades, not having time to study, and a lot of pressure.

To the question about the school atmosphere whether it is welcoming, safe, pressing, demanding, or other, some of the replies came to be positive with 33% feeling comfortable and welcomed, and 25% feeling safe as shown in Table 19.

In Table 20, 47% of the replies show that those students are satisfied with the relationship and friendship with their friends, and that 33% like the way teachers teach.

Table 18

Interview Question. What is Your Definition of a Good School? Do you See Your school Like That?

Answers	Grouped Answers by Topic	Frequency	Percentage
1	Good teacher-student relationship	2	9%
2	Teachers having experience	2	9%
3	Teaching students to be better	3	13%
4	School with good education/high standards of education	5	22%
5	Restricting bullying	1	4%
6	School providing safe/comfortable environment	5	22%
7	School concentrating on activities/social skills not just education	2	9%
8	School respecting/appreciating students	3	13%
	Totals	23	100%

Table 19

Interview Question. Describe Your School Atmosphere. Welcoming, Safe, Pressing, Demanding

Answers	Grouped Answers by Topic	Frequency	Percentage
1	Comfortable atmosphere/welcoming	8	33%
2	Safe	6	25%
3	Strict	2	8%
4	Bullying	2	8%
5	Teachers are understanding / flexible	2	8%
6	Administration neglecting student problems / Not flexible	4	17%
	Totals	24	100%

Table 20

Interview Question. What One Thing You Like Most About Your School?

Answers	Grouped Answers by Topic	Frequency	Percentage
1	The way of teaching/teachers	5	33%
2	I like everything about this school/ Welcoming Atmosphere	3	20%
3	Relationship / friendship between students / my friends	7	47%
	Totals	15	100%

Table 21 indicates that 6 students/responses out of 10 interviewed, representing 33%, feel the school rules and regulations are strict, and 5 students, representing 28%, believe the school rules and regulations are unfair, not flexible, and not logical. It is remarkable that another 6 students, representing 33%; 11% and 22%, feel school rules and regulations are not strict but fair, logical, and made for the good of the students.

Table 21

Interview Question. How do You See the School Rules and Regulations?

Answers	Grouped Answers by Topic	Frequency	Percentage
1	Not Strict/fair	2	11%
2	Made for our Good / logical	4	22%
3	Strict	6	33%
4	Same as any school	1	6%
5	Unfair/not flexible/ not logical	5	28%
	Totals	18	100%

As shown in Table 22, students gave different answers about the subjects they like and the reasons for that, yet three students acknowledged that it depends on the teacher.

Table 22

Interview Question. What Subject Do You Enjoy Most? Why?

Answers	Grouped Answers by Topic	Frequency	Percentage
1	Math (I don't feel bored/great teacher/easy subject)	3	27%
2	Arabic (love this subject)	1	9%
3	Physics (interesting subject/ great teacher)	2	18%
4	English (good teacher)	1	9%
5	Biology (I want to be a medical doctor/ interesting subject)	2	18%
6	Chemistry (no reason)	1	9%
7	PE (not sitting in class)	1	9%
	Totals	11	100%

Table 23 indicates that at 25% of EHS students are under pressure of getting good grades and maintaining high average. Another 25% expressed that their most challenge is being bullied or teased.

Students also described their teachers and their relationship with them as unfavorable where 6 responses, representing 26%, said that some teachers are not good, they don't make an effort, and they are mean. On the contrary, all other remarks, aggregated to 74%, came to be positive, as shown below in Table 24.

Interview Question. What Has Been Most Challenging to You in this School and Why?

Answers	Grouped Answers by Topic	Frequency	Percentage
1	Nothing	2	17%
2	Getting good grades/maintaining high average	3	25%
3	Recognize by Teachers/difficulty with some teachers	2	17%
4	Being bullied/teased	3	25%
5	Not having time to study/ a lot of pressure	2	17%
	Totals	12	100%

Table 24

Interview Question. In What Words Do You Describe Your Teachers and Your Relationship with Them?

Answers	Grouped Answers by Topic	Frequency	Percentage
1	Loving/caring	4	17%
2	Good relationship with some teachers	5	22%
3	Teachers are good/very good	4	17%
4	Friendly	2	9%
5	Give support & help	2	9%
6	Some teachers are not good/ don't make an effort /mean	6	26%
	Totals	23	100%

When students were asked if they would recommend EHS to a friend or relative and give reasons, most students' responses came to be positive except for 20% who expressed a negative answer as they feel lacks activities and needs improvement as Table 25 shows.

Table 25

Interview Question. Would You Recommend this School to a Friend or Relative and Why?

Answers	Grouped Answers by Topic	Frequency	Percentage
1	Yes, it's a good school /good teachers	3	15%
2	Yes, helps students succeed /good education	4	20%
3	Yes, good atmosphere / very friendly / comfortable / safe	9	45%
4	Maybe, when school improves	1	5%
5	No, for the time being / not enough activities	3	15%
	Totals	20	100%

When asked about one thing they like to change, 50% of aggregated responses revolving about changing the curriculum including tests and exams and adding activities. Another 19% would like teachers to stop favoritism as Table 26 shows.

Table 26

Interview Question. What is the One Thing You Would Like to Change in Your School?

Answers	Grouped Answers by Topic	Frequency	Percentage
1	Curriculum / applying the curriculum (tests, exams)	4	25%
2	Nothing	1	6%
3	Changing the location	1	6%
4	Changing the rules/ some rules	3	19%
5	School atmosphere (adding activities/being creative)	4	25%
6	Stop favoritism/ bullying	3	19%
	Totals	16	100%

In the last question of the interviews, as shown in Table 27, all students expressed their attachment to school when asked whether they would go to another school if given the chance and what would be the reasons, except one response due to the lack of activities and a lot of pressure.

Table 27

Interview Question. If You Were Given the Chance to Leave to Another School, Would You Go? What Would be the Reason?

Answers	Grouped Answers by Topic	Frequency	Percentage
1	No, I got used to it	2	14%
2	No, I love my teachers	1	7%
3	No, it's the best school in the area	1	7%
4	No, I'm very happy here / love this school	3	21%
5	No, high standard of education & support	2	14%
6	No, I'm part of the school / family / home	4	29%
7	Yes, lack of activities & a lot of pressure	1	7%
	Totals	14	100%

Step by Step Graph Analysis of the Data to Answer the Research Questions:

In order to reach the conclusion of why students leave EHS or have intentions to leave, a graph is developed, Figure 39, which provides a systematic roadmap, a step by step process to answer the research questions (RQ) below:

RQ # 1: Which of the following demographics: grade level, family status, family income, years of continuous education, means of transportation, and student rank affect student satisfaction resulting in students intending to leave EHS?

Student Satisfaction Survey (SSS) Steps of Data Analysis

Figure 39. Step by step analysis of the data to answer the research questions.

RQ # 2: Is there a relationship between each of the following school climate domains and student satisfaction: (1) Personal/Social Environment, (2) Physical Environment, (3) Learning/Cognitive Environment, and (4) Moral Environment?

RQ # 3: What factors of school climate or demographics at EHS are causing student intention to leave school?

The steps are as follows:

- **To answer RQ # 1, we will do steps 1 and 2:**

Step 1: Regression on Satisfaction against Demographics (half of RQ 1).

Step 2: Cross-Tabulating Future Variable “I’m Leaving EHS” with Satisfaction (half of RQ 1)

- **To answer RQ # 2, we will do step 3:**

Step 3: Correlation between the four domains as Variables and Satisfaction (RQ 2)

- **To answer RQ # 3, we will do steps 4 and 5:**

Step 4: Cross-Tabulation between Demographics and Future Status (Intention to leave EHS) (half of RQ 3)

Step 5: Cross-Tabulation and Correlation between “I’m Leaving EHS” and the Four Domains (half of RQ 3)

Step 1: The Effect of Demographics on Student Satisfaction.

We implemented the regression method using demographics as independent variable and the Question 30 in the SSS as the dependent variable (Appendix D) to determine which demographic variable shows significance level towards Satisfaction.

When using the regression model on satisfaction against demographic variable, Table 28 clearly shows that the variable significant were “mothers” with 0.040 and “education” with a significant value of 0.049 (lower than 0.05); whereas,

no significance was found for any other variable since their values were higher than 0.05. When examining the beta value for education it showed a negative value of -.266, which indicated an inversely proportional value against satisfaction. Step 1 is clearly showing that satisfaction is higher in lower classes/levels and as education levels increase the level of satisfaction decreases. This takes us back to students' answer in Learning/Cognitive question number 19 in the survey about EHS educational level where 75% of 171 students considered EHS educational level being high. As some students reached higher classes they started to feel the academic pressure and consequently could not cope and thus left EHS for a less demanding school.

Table 28

Regression Method on Satisfaction Against Demographics

Coefficients ^a						
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	<i>t</i>	Sig.	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
	(Constant)	3.969	1.006		3.945	.000
	1.gender	.267	.187	.131	1.431	.155
	2.class	-.008	.069	-.014	-.122	.903
	3.family	.169	.454	.036	.373	.710
	4.father	.063	.177	.035	.358	.721
1	5.mother	-.391	.189	-.216	-2.073	.040
	6.work	.014	.174	.008	.081	.936
	7.income	.212	.126	.158	1.681	.096
	8.education	-.266	.134	-.181	-1.988	.049
	9.transport	.128	.107	.111	1.199	.233
	10.rank	-.026	.121	-.021	-.219	.827
	11.future	-.078	.152	-.058	-.513	.609

a. Dependent Variable: M30.I'm satisfied with my experience at EHS

As for “mothers” with significant value of 0.040 and beta value of -.391, it also shows that the relationship is inversely proportional. This means that as mothers were more highly educated, students were less satisfied, and vice versa. The SSS did not include the mothers in the survey, so there is no information why this effect is taking place. Could it be that educated mothers feel with the pressure of the high educational level and were not satisfied with the school and consequently pass this dissatisfaction to their children? This is an item that may merit further study in the future.

In these steps we are taking, we are trying to narrow down our analysis, after discovering that there is a problem in education as we have seen, to find where specifically the problem is; in class, education, or rank that is making EHS student intend to leave. Step 2 will shed more light on this discussion.

Step 2: Cross-Tabulating Future Variable “I’m Leaving EHS” with Satisfaction

Table 29 shows that 10 students responded with “I’m Leaving EHS”. It also indicates that the top two dissatisfaction categories (Strongly disagree, disagree) count for 60% of students who mentioned that they have intention to leave EHS. In other words 6 students out of the 10, expressing their intention to leave, responded that they are not satisfied with their experience at EHS.

When we correlate the four variables regarding students leaving EHS, we notice from Table 30 that not all variables tested have a significance lower than 0.05 which indicates that all variables relate to each other and are significant where the strongest relationship in general is between Personal/Social and Moral environment having $r = 0.890$ affecting students of “Leaving EHS” or those who expressed their intention to leave EHS, while the weakest was between Personal/Social and Physical environment with $r = 0.663$. For Physical the strongest correlation was with

Learning/Cognitive with $r=0.881$, for Learning/Cognitive the strongest correlation was with Physical with $r=0.881$, and for Moral the strongest correlation was with Personal/Social with $r=0.890$. We need to keep in mind that this correlation is done on a very small sample of 10 students who responded with “Leaving EHS.”

Table 29

Cross-tabulation between Satisfaction and Future

Count		11.future	
		leave EHS to another school	Total
M30. I'm satisfied with my experience at EHS	strongly disagree	2	2
	disagree	4	4
	neutral	1	1
	agree	1	1
	strongly agree	2	2
Total number of Students with Intention to Leave EHS		10	10

Step 3: Correlation between the Four Domains as Variables and Satisfaction

When correlating the four domain variables of school climate with satisfaction we noticed, as shown in Table 31, that the significant values for all four variables were below 0.05 thus observing significance for all variables when correlated to satisfaction. This correlation is found to be positively and directly correlated with a strong correlation.

Table 30

Correlation Table with 4 Variables Regarding Students Leaving EHS

Correlations		AVG Personal/ Social	AVG physical	AVG Learn/ Cognitive	AVG Moral
AVG Personal/ Social	Pearson Correlation	1	.476	.663*	.890**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.164	.037	.001
	N	10	10	10	10
AVG physical	Pearson Correlation	.476	1	.881**	.556
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.164		.001	.095
	N	10	10	10	10
AVG Learning/ Cognitive	Pearson Correlation	.663*	.881**	1	.699*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.037	.001		.025
	N	10	10	10	10
AVG Moral	Pearson Correlation	.890**	.556	.699*	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.001	.095	.025	
	N	10	10	10	10

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 31

Checking the Relationship between Student Satisfaction and the Four Domains

Satisfaction		AVG Personal/ Social	AVG Physical	AVG Learning/ Cognitive	AVG Moral
	r	.575**	.490**	.469**	.769**
M30. I'm satisfied with my experience at EHS	Sig. (2- tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	171	171	171	171

It is remarkable how Satisfaction "I'm satisfied with my experience at EHS" correlated extremely high with Moral at .769 and Personal/Social at .575 domains.

While the least correlated domain was found to be at Learning/Cognitive .469, which gave a clear view that questions on Learning/Cognitive when correlated to satisfaction gave the least set of positive outcomes. In other words, students were satisfied with the Personal/Social and Moral experience at EHS, and at the same time they were not fully satisfied with the Physical environment (.490) and more dissatisfied with the high level of education. This conclusion confirmed the previous analysis.

Step 4: Cross-Tabulation and Regression between Demographics and Future Status (Intention to Leave EHS)

As we narrowed our analysis, the regression model in Table 32 showed the only variables with significance were Class and Education with significance lower than 0.05, while the third one Rank in the demographics had value greater than 0.05 consequently Rank has no relation or significance whatsoever to the dependent variable Future for those intention to leave EHS. This regression table was an added value to our previous explanation. These findings were very useful and critical. In some cases new students joined EHS from another school and they suffered the high level of education. However, these findings also told us that EHS students who declared leaving EHS in the future had started as early as preschool and lower elementary and upon reaching Grade 7 and some others Grade 10 started to find the educational level difficult for them.

As shown in Table 33, when we cross-tabulated between leaving EHS and some variables of demographics we noticed that 70% of those who had intention to leave EHS were found in Grade 7 and Grade 10, and 80% had been in EHS from lower levels of education (Elementary, Preschool). As commonly known, in Grade 7 and Grade 10 students start encountering new subjects that are not in Grade 6 such as

Chemistry, Biology, and Physics or Grade 9 such as Sociology and Economics. As such, the weak students suffer and the only solution they have is to “exit” the school.

Table 32

Cross-Tabulation and Regression between Demographics and Future Status just for those Have Intention to Leave EHS)

Coefficients						
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
	(Constant)	2.317	.496		4.676	.000
1	2.Class	.237	.036	.513	6.542	.000
	8.Education	.120	.079	.112	1.529	.029
	10.rank	-.094	.073	-.100	-1.289	.200

Note. Dependent Variable: 11.future

Table 33

Cross-tabulation between Demographics and Leaving the EHS

1. Class	Count	Intention to leave EHS to another school
Grade 7	3	30.0%
Grade 8	1	10.0%
Grade 9	1	10.0%
Grade 10	4	40.0%
Grade 11	1	10.0%
8. Education		Intention to leave EHS to another school
Preschool	5	50.0%
Elementary	3	30.0%
Intermediate	1	10.0%
Secondary	1	10.0%

To find out if there is any significance between Class and the four domains of school climate, and between Education and the four domains, we used the regression method for Class vs. the four domains as variables with “Future Status” as dependent variable.

The two variables with direct significance to the dependent variable Future came to be the Physical and Personal/Social with a significance value lower than 0.05. However, they seemed to have an opposite relation with Physical having an inversely proportional effect (negative effect) while the Personal/Social had a positive effect value. In other words, as students increased 1 level of class, the Personal/Social experience of school climate increased by 0.349, as indicated in Table 34, while the physical environment decreased by .325 .

Table 34

Checking the Significance between Class vs. Four Domains as Variables

Coefficients						
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients			
	B	Std. Error	Beta	<i>t</i>	Sig.	
	(Constant)	1.684	.907		1.857	.065
	AVG Personal/Social	1.003	.327	.349	3.066	.003
1	AVG Physical	-.865	.252	-.325	-3.438	.001
	AVG Learning/Cognitive	.114	.323	.035	.354	.724
	AVG Moral	.103	.274	.043	.377	.707

Note. Dependent Variable: 11. future

What was obvious in Table 35, as opposite regression, was that the Moral variable had the only significant effect with a significant value lower than 0.05. It seemed that it had an inversely proportional effect on the dependent variable education (negative effect). In other words, as students advanced in education their moral experience (of school climate) become weaker. This result confirms previous findings.

Table 35

Checking the Significance between Education vs. Four Domains as Variables

Coefficients						
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients			
	B	Std. Error	Beta	<i>t</i>	Sig.	
	(Constant)	1.628	.433		3.760	.000
	AVG Personal/Social	.078	.156	.059	.497	.620
1	AVG Physical	.200	.120	.164	1.665	.098
	AVG Learn/Cognitive	.046	.154	.031	.301	.764
	AVG Moral	-.358	.131	-.325	-2.738	.007

a. Dependent Variable: 8. education

Table 36 confirmed the conclusion discussed previously that as some students moved to upper grades they found it difficult to continue. Their weaknesses were revealed by the high educational standard of the school. So, 40% of those planning to “*Leave EHS to another school*” ranked below 60. In other words 4 out of the 10 students who answered that they have intention to leave EHS to another school were weak students who were not happy with their performance at school.

Step 5: Cross-Tabulation and Correlation Between I'm leaving EHS and the Four Domains

Table 37 shows the means of the four domains for the 10 students who stated leaving EHS to be significant. However, the Physical domain shows the least mean amongst all domains (3.040) followed directly by the Moral domain (3.090). It is clearly shown that these two domains were an indication of the more influential reason of why students expressed their intention to leave EHS.

Table 36

Cross-tabulation between Future and Rank

11.future * 10.rank Cross-Tabulation						
Count		10.rank				Total
		below 60	between 61 & 75	between 76 & 85	Between 86 & 100	
	graduating this year	0	12	6	3	21
	want to graduate from EHS	1	39	54	34	128
11.future	leave EHS to another school	4	0	4	2	10
	leave EHS as I'm travelling	0	2	3	1	6
Total		5	53	67	40	165

In this regression model in Table 38 we can notice that the only variable with significance was Moral with significance 0.007, lower than 0.05, while other variables had value greater than 0.05. Thus, we conclude that there was no relation or significance whatsoever to the dependent variable satisfaction except for Moral. Thus, for each increase of 1 unit in Moral there will be a 1.273 decreasing in “leaving EHS.”

Table 37

Means of the Ten Leaving Students on the Four Domains

Descriptive Statistics	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
AVG Personal/Social	3.100	.5617	10
AVG Physical	3.040	.6603	10
AVG Learning/Cognitive	3.370	.5579	10
AVG Moral	3.090	.8825	10

Table 38

Regression between 4 Domains and “Leaving EHS”

Coefficients ^a						
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients			
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.	
	(Constant)	.063	1.435		.044	.967
	AVG Personal/Social	.485	.755	.182	.642	.549
1	AVG physical	-.850	.625	-.376	-1.360	.232
	AVG Learning/Cognitive	1.516	.866	.566	1.749	.141
	AVG moral	-2.156	.487	-1.273	-4.430	.007

a. Dependent Variable: leaving EHS

When correlating the 10 leaving students with the Four Domains, the figures in Table 39 showed a strong relation between Personal/Social and Moral domains. Therefore, those 10 students who indicated their intention to leave EHS showed dissatisfaction with the Personal/Social and Moral experiences more than with the

Physical and Learning/Cognitive experience. Both domains, the Personal/Social and the Moral domain contained items such as relationship with teachers, enrolling their children in the future at EHS, and satisfying experience, which is more likely resulted in leaving the school in the future.

Table 39

Correlation of the Ten Leaving Students with the Four Domains

	Correlations	AVG Personal/ Social	AVG Physical	AVG learning/ Cognitive	AVG Moral
AVG Personal/ Social	Pearson Correlation	1	.476	.663*	.890**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.164	.037	.001
	N	10	10	10	10
AVG Physical	Pearson Correlation	.476	1	.881**	.556
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.164		.001	.095
	N	10	10	10	10
AVG Learning/ Cognitive	Pearson Correlation	.663*	.881**	1	.699*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.037	.001		.025
	N	10	10	10	10
AVG Moral	Pearson Correlation	.890**	.556	.699*	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.001	.095	.025	
	N	10	10	10	10

Note. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2 tailed) and at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

CHAPTER 5

CONCLUSION

In this chapter, we give a summary of the data analyzed and draw conclusions of the influential factors that are “pushing” students to think of leaving school. EHS has the qualifications of a good school as this research has shown. The steps to the solution for why students reach a stage to think of leaving were highlighted in this study.

Summary and Conclusions

In this section, a summary is drawn with conclusions from our research about school climate and students intention to leave School. For an efficient way to conclude, we follow the pattern of answering the research questions.

1. Which of the following demographics: grade level, family status, family income, years of continuous education, means of transportation, and student rank affect student satisfaction resulting in students intending to leave EHS?
2. Is there a relationship between each of the following school climate domains and student satisfaction: (1) Personal/Social Environment, (2) Physical Environment, (3) Learning/Cognitive Environment, and (4) Moral Environment?
3. What factors of school climate or demographics at EHS are causing student intention to leave school?

Responding to Research Questions

In the following section, we will respond to each of the research questions (RQ) and draw conclusions.

RQ 1: Demographics and Student Satisfaction

In the demographics only two domains seemed to effect, inter-correlate, and have proper significance over all the dependent variables and over the four domains, which were the Future Status and Education. When dealing with the total sample Future Status was taken as dependent, but when we looked further into the 10 students in Future Status item the Students Leaving EHS was taken as sub-variable or dependent.

In the Future Status of “Students Intention to leave EHS” item shows that grade 7 and grade 10 are the most influential on student intention to leave EHS. Those precisely were actually not satisfied and had shown the highest percentages in disagreeing and strongly disagreeing and their intention to leave. Also, consistency of continuing from lower levels to higher levels were greatly shown since 73% of the sample were students that registered from preschool and continued on to higher educational levels. As we have seen in step 2, 10 students responded that they intend to leave, where 8 out of 10 students have joined EHS from the preschool, while 2 students joined in secondary level. The high academic level of the school in Secondary classes is pressuring students to think of leaving EHS to a less demanding school.

When cross-tabulating Satisfaction “I’m Satisfied with my experience at EHS” among those who intention to leave EHS we noticed that 60% of them were dissatisfied. Therefore, there might be an indication that they intend to leave strictly because they were not satisfied with their experience at EHS.

RQ2: School Climate and Student Satisfaction

In the section of school climate and the analysis of the four domains vs. satisfaction it was noted that the Physical domain as well as the Learning/Cognitive domain had the two lowest mean scores which was an indication that these were the main disadvantage of why students were dissatisfied.

When cross-tabulating the four domains with the demographics, the means showed the same problem of having Education and Class as the above with the same negative features thus proving our data assumptions related to education and class and their effect on the students' satisfaction to be right.

When cross-tabulated with the four domains, the average mean of dissatisfaction was higher in Physical and Learning/Cognitive than in Personal/Social and Moral. However, all four domains had a seemingly low mean averaged slightly above 3 which was also near to neutral with an indication of not agreeing at being satisfied in all four domains except for Moral domain which had a slightly higher mean than others.

In other words, students were satisfied with the Personal/Social and Moral experience at EHS, and at the same time they were not fully satisfied with the Physical environment and more dissatisfied with the high level of education.

RQ3: School Climate and Intention to Leave

When correlating the four domains for those who intend to leave EHS, we noticed that there was significance with high relation of positive correlation between Personal/Social and Moral followed directly by Physical and Learning/Cognitive. This can be interpreted as Personal/Social and Moral domain when either of them is positive it affects positively the other and vice versa, and this is also true for Physical and Learning/Cognitive.

The highest mean among all the four domains was found for Personal/Social environment, and the least was found for Physical environment. However, when we further studied the statements constituting each domain we noticed that even though the Personal/Social environment topped the highest with a mean of 3.605 out of 5, yet, it had a statement that did not reflect high mean which was the enrollment of children in the future at EHS that scored 2.74 only. This could be interrelated to issues such as those registered in the qualitative question, in the Remark section of SSS. We find similar issue in the rest of the domains where a statement did not reflect high mean.

The weight of the students' dissatisfaction concentrated mainly on three areas of the school climate. The qualitative responses gave more detailed feedback about student's satisfaction and dissatisfaction. The qualitative responses supported our conclusion that the quantitative study had shown. As discussed previously, here is a summary of the influential factors that were "pushing" students to think of leaving EHS:

1. EHS students, even if enrolled from Preschool, encountered difficulty in Grade 7 and Grade 10. Also, new students joining EHS at Grade 7 and above did not continue at EHS due to the high academic requirements of the Secondary level.
2. Students' experience was not satisfactory due to the absence of some physical aspects such as library, labs, and after-school Activities. Students compared their school with other schools and finally left to a school that met their expectations. Marks (1998) argued that the attitude of students towards their school was an important predictor of whether they would stay or leave school. This meant that students with a negative attitude towards their school were

most likely to leave school while students with a positive attitude towards their school were less likely to leave even if both groups were achieving the same results (Marks, 1998).

3. Third was the teachers' attitude. One aspect of school climate that was driving students to leave school was the teachers. It was obvious that the most important negative responses with high percentages concentrated on: teachers, problems in teachers' behavior as they did not treat everyone equally, and even "some teachers must change." Teachers mocked students with low achievement as our survey has shown.

Figure 40 below shows the steps taken in manipulating the data we have from the SSS in order to answer our research questions. It also shows the main results of the analysis.

Figure 40. The conceptual framework and the main results of the analysis.

Limitations

- Although the Student Satisfaction Survey (SSS) was carried out in one school, in our case EHS, still schools of similar situation can benefit from the findings.
- The SSS as well as the interviews were limited to the feedback of students from Grade 7 to Grade 12.
- The SSS was not able to measure how much the *Financial Status* was a factor for students intention to leave school as they usually do not know their parents income. The SSS survey showed that 47% of *both parents worked* and only 48% *the father worked*. Also, the highest family income range was for family income between 500 and 2,000 USD. All this data meant that approximately more than two fifth of the sample belonged to the middle or lower class of the society. The SSS surveyed students without parent involvement.
- The school has provided us with the necessary statistics that were used to compare with our results; however, this was limited to what the school considered public information.

Recommendations

I hope the analysis of the data will identify the strengths and the areas for improvement for the Evangelical Heritage School wishing to reduce students intention to leaving school. Improving EHS climate will be a predictor of its success (Raman, Chi Ling & Khalid, 2015). Since the only positive feedback came for a single response (Best school) with a rather high response of 20%, high relatively for a single response, EHS should continue to maintain this good reputation and take into consideration several important factors listed below:

- Since most of the students surveyed live with their parents (92%) they are presumably still family oriented. Also, as both parents (fathers and mothers) belong to the category of the highly educated especially those having a university degree 68% for fathers and 62% for mothers, their children are less likely to leave school (Marks, 1998). Therefore, EHS should involve the family in its communication.
- Students with good grades between 76 and 100 were the majority with 65%, which was a good indicator on the levels of education in the school, and those having average scores constituted 32%, with only 3% out of the total sample failing. All in all, the percentage of success is 97%. EHS administration should find a balance between the desired educational level and student satisfaction with focus on Grade 7 and Grade 10. Most people who expressed their intention to leave were from those classes. This can be done through the subject coordinators who should work on smoothing the gap between elementary level and intermediate level focusing on Grade 6 and Grade 7 respectively, and the gap between intermediate level and secondary level focusing on Grade 9 and Grade 10 respectively. Since Grade 7 and Grade 10 are not official exams classes, a reconsideration of the new subjects and the load of material is worth taking.
- Surprisingly, 78% out of the total sample wanted to graduate from EHS; this percentage aligned with the percentage of 73% of the sample that were enrolled from preschool. This implies that consistency and the continuity that starts from early and beginning education has higher chances to continue on and finally graduate from EHS. Students develop some sort of attachment to EHS. So when a student decides to leave then it is worth investigating why.

EHS should implement “Exit Interview” or “Withdrawal Interview” with those who intention to leave to gather information on the reasons of leaving and show that the EHS really cares for its students, even those who decided to leave.

- The qualitative feedback and the interviews of students revealed a lot of hidden data that quantitative analysis could not show. Thus, when quantifying the qualitative data we could now relate a lot of why some questions in some domains had lower means and this was clearly shown from the 62% responses stated. Students have the right to be heard and EHS should find a way to hear the students’ voices and gather feedback constantly to evaluate student satisfaction. This will help the administration in which way decisions should be taken and improvements could be implemented.
- EHS should work on the improvement of facilities, services, and activities as the feedback came high with 55% that focused on the physical aspect of school climate. Many schools around EHS have worked on the improvement of their facilities, busses, as well as adding new services for students with special needs. Now-a-days, parents look for a school that gives the most outcome to their investment from Nursery classes to the Secondary level.
- EHS should put a strategy to prevent students from reaching the decision to leave the school. First, the school could track student performance at Cycle 1 (Grade 1, 2 and 3) in order to predict the future performance and start a prevention program for such students (CARMA, n.d.). Second, empower the counselor of the school to alarm the administration of any case of student dissatisfaction, and use their reports to identify prospect leaving students.

Third, EHS should come up with more sports and after school activities to create student-school attachment.

EHS needs to emphasize and strengthen what the school is doing right (Voigt & Hundrieser, 2008), and implement the recommendations in order to retain students at school until graduation. As a lot of research has been focused on college and university level, and very little work has been done on student retention in K-12 schools, I hope this study will provide useful information and suggestions to help the EHS and other schools retain its students and more than that to develop a plan to attract more students.

Recommendations for Further Research

- There has been a lot of studies done on college and university level on student satisfaction, student retention, student leaving, and student dropout. Further studies should be carried on K-12 level to provide principals with recommendations on student retention. Such studies will be beneficial if they survey what happens after students leave school. Terms such as dropout, push out, pull out, class retention, and transfer to another school could be the focus of such study.
- It is interesting and worth researching when data about educated mothers gave a significant value of 0.040 and beta value of -.391 in relation to students' satisfaction. The relationship came to be inversely proportional meaning that as mothers were high in education students were less satisfied and vice versa. Could it be that educated mothers feel the pressure of the high educational level and were dissatisfied with the school and consequently pass this dissatisfaction to their children! Could it be that educated mothers put pressure

on their children to achieve well in this competitive atmosphere? There was an indication that is worth researching.

- The Student Satisfaction Survey surveyed students from Grade 7 till Grade 12. However, Grades 4, 5, and 6 could have shed more light if they were involved.
- The Student Satisfaction Survey, designed by the researcher of this study, can be modified and developed to survey parents on possible factors such as the financial status. It is also worth knowing the parents' point of view and satisfaction as parents affect the decision of student retention at school.

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APPENDIX A

SCHOOL SATISFACTION SURVEY (SSS)

Dear Student,

I would like you to spend a few minutes to answer the following questionnaire about your satisfaction with EHS climate. The aim of this questionnaire is to improve the school performance and student experience, so please answer with honesty.

Your answers will be strictly confidential and anonymous as you are not required to identify your name. Thank you.

Years of Continuous Education	
1. Gender:	<input type="checkbox"/> Female <input type="checkbox"/> Male
2. Class:	<input type="checkbox"/> Grade7 <input type="checkbox"/> Grade 8 <input type="checkbox"/> Grade 9 <input type="checkbox"/> Grade 10 <input type="checkbox"/> Grade 11 <input type="checkbox"/> Grade 12

Family Status	
1.	<input type="checkbox"/> I live with my parents <input type="checkbox"/> I live with my mother <input type="checkbox"/> I live with my Father <input type="checkbox"/> I live with my grand-parents
2.	<input type="checkbox"/> My father had no education <input type="checkbox"/> My father has High School <input type="checkbox"/> My father has university degree
3.	<input type="checkbox"/> My mother had no education <input type="checkbox"/> My mother has High School <input type="checkbox"/> My mother has university degree

Family Income	
1.	<input type="checkbox"/> Both parents work <input type="checkbox"/> Only my father works <input type="checkbox"/> Only my mother works
2.	Family monthly income is between: <input type="checkbox"/> \$500-\$2000 <input type="checkbox"/> \$2001-\$5000 <input type="checkbox"/> More than \$5000

Starting Education at EHS	
<input type="checkbox"/> Preschool <input type="checkbox"/> Elementary <input type="checkbox"/> Intermediate <input type="checkbox"/> Secondary	

Means of Transportation	
<input type="checkbox"/> I come by School Bus <input type="checkbox"/> I come by private minivan/Taxi <input type="checkbox"/> My parents bring me to school	

Grade Rank	
<input type="checkbox"/> Below 60 <input type="checkbox"/> Between 61 & 75 <input type="checkbox"/> Between 76 & 85 <input type="checkbox"/> Between 86 - 100	

Future Status	
<input type="checkbox"/> I'm Graduating this year	<input type="checkbox"/> I want to graduate from EHS
<input type="checkbox"/> I'm leaving EHS to another school	
<input type="checkbox"/> I'm leaving EHS as we are moving our house	<input type="checkbox"/> I'm leaving EHS as I'm travelling

SD = Strongly Disagree D = Disagree N = Neutral A = Agree SA =

Strongly Agree

Please check ✓ one item of each row that best describes your answer:

Personal/Social Environment (P)	SD	D	N	A	SA
1. I feel EHS is my home.					
2. I'm treated as an individual.					
3. I'm in good relationship with my teachers					
4. "Open, honest and active communication occurs between teachers-students, and teachers-parents." (NCCS, n.d.)					
5. My family considers EHS warm, inviting and helpful.					
6. My parents are proud of EHS results in the official exams.					
7. EHS has good reputation in the community.					
8. In the future, I will enroll my children at EHS.					
Physical Environment (PH)	SD	D	N	A	SA
1. "Classrooms and grounds are clean and well-maintained." (NCCS, n.d.)					
2. School and classrooms are rich with displays of works created by students.					
3. I'm satisfied with EHS library					
4. I'm satisfied with EHS playground					
5. I'm satisfied with EHS labs					
6. The canteen provides what I need.					
7. Students feel safe everywhere on EHS property					
8. EHS rules and regulations regarding safety and expected behavior are clear.					

Learning/Cognitive Environment (L)	SD	D	N	A	SA
1. Students are encouraged to succeed.					
2. Expectations are high for all students.					
3. EHS educational level is very high					
4. "Achievements and performance are rewarded, praised and publicly displayed." (NCCS, nd)					
5. Students are assigned to research, prepare a presentation, and present in class.					
6. Progress is monitored, evaluated regularly, and shared with parents.					
7. I'm satisfied with afterschool activities					
8. Teachers are caring and supportive.					
9. Classroom size and ratio of students-to-teacher are helpful to learning.					
Moral Environment (M)	SD	D	N	A	SA
1. EHS values diversity and is welcoming to all cultures.					
2. EHS has built my character with values and respect.					
3. "Staff, students, and families demonstrate school pride. National Center for Community School." (NCCS, nd).					
4. EHS and its educational program include development of knowledge/skills that promote ethical decision-making and conflict resolution.					
5. I'm satisfied with my experience at EHS					

(OPEN END QUESTION)

My Remarks:

APPENDIX B
INTERVIEW QUESTIONS

1. What is your definition of a good school?
2. Describe your school atmosphere? Welcoming, safe, pressing, demanding...?
3. What one thing you like most about your school?
4. How do you see the school rules and regulation?
5. What subject do you enjoy most? Why?
6. What has been most challenging to you in this school and why?
7. In what words do you describe your teachers and your relationship with them?
8. Would you recommend this school to a friend or relative and why?
9. What is the one thing you would like to change in your school?
10. If you were given the chance to leave to another school, would you go?
What would be the reasons?

APPENDIX C

INTERVIEW RESPONSES

1) **What is your definition of a good school?**

- I.Good teacher-student relationship
- II.Teachers having experience
- III.Teaching students to be better
- IV.School with good education/high standards of education
- V.Restricting bullying
- VI.School providing safe/comfortable environment
- VII.School concentrating on activities/social skills not just education

- VIII.School respecting/appreciating students

Code List	Code 1	Code 2	Code 3	Code 4	Code 5	Code 6	Code 7	Code 8	Total
Frequency	2	2	3	5	1	5	2	3	23
Percentage	9%	9%	13%	22%	4%	22%	9%	13%	100%

2) **Describe your school atmosphere. Welcoming, safe, pressing, demanding...**

- I.Comfortable atmosphere/welcoming
- II.Safe
- III.Strict
- IV.Bullying
- V.Teachers are understanding / flexible
- VI.Administration neglecting student problems / Not flexible

Code List	Code1	Code2	Code3	Code4	Code5	Code6	Total
Frequency	8	6	2	2	2	4	24
Percentage	33%	25%	8%	8%	8%	17%	100%

3) **What one thing you like most about your school?**

- I.The way of teaching/teachers
- II.I like everything about this school/ Welcoming Atmosphere
- III.Relationship / friendship between students / my friends

Code List	Code1	Code2	Code3	Total
Frequency	5	3	7	15
Percentage	33%	20%	47%	100%

4) How do you see the school rules and regulations?

- I. Not Strict/fair
- II. Made for our Good / logical
- III. Strict
- IV. Same as any school
- V. Unfair/not flexible/ not logical

Code List	Code1	Code2	Code3	Code4	Code5	Total
Frequency	2	4	6	1	5	18
Percentage	11%	22%	33%	6%	28%	100%

5) What subject do you enjoy most? Why?

- I. Math (I don't feel bored/great teacher/easy subject)
- II. Arabic (love this subject)
- III. Physics (interesting subject/ great teacher)
- IV. English (good teacher)
- V. Biology (I want to be a medical doctor/ interesting subject)
- VI. Chemistry (no reason)
- VII. PE (not sitting in class)

Code List	Code1	Code2	Code3	Code4	Code5	Code6	Code7	Total
Frequency	3	1	2	1	2	1	1	11
Percentage	27%	9%	18%	9%	18%	9%	9%	100%

6) What has been most challenging to you in this school and why?

- I. Nothing
- II. Getting good grades/maintaining high average
- III. Recognize by Teachers/difficulty with some teachers
- IV. Being bullied/teased
- V. Not having time to study/ a lot of pressure

Code List	Code1	Code2	Code3	Code4	Code5	Total
Frequency	2	3	2	3	2	12
Percentage	17%	25%	17%	25%	17%	100%

7) In what words do you describe your teachers and your relationship with them?

- I. Loving/caring
- II. Good relationship with some teachers
- III. Teachers are good/very good
- IV. Friendly
- V. Give support and help
- VI. Some teachers are not good/ don't make an effort /mean

Code List	Code1	Code2	Code3	Code4	Code5	Code6	Total
Frequency	4	5	4	2	2	6	23
Percentage	17%	22%	17%	9%	9%	26%	100%

8) Would you recommend this school to a friend or relative and why?

- I. Yes, it's a good school / good teachers
- II. Yes, helps students succeed / good education
- III. Yes, good atmosphere / very friendly / comfortable / safe
- IV. Maybe, when school improves
- V. No, for the time being / not enough activities

Code List	Code1	Code2	Code3	Code4	Code5	Total
Frequency	3	4	9	1	3	20
Percentage	15%	20%	45%	5%	15%	100%

9) What is the one thing you would like to change in your school?

- I. Curriculum / applying the curriculum (tests, exams)
- II. Nothing
- III. Changing the location
- IV. Changing the rules/ some rules
- V. School atmosphere (adding activities/being creative)
- VI. Stop favoritism/ bullying

Code List	Code1	Code2	Code3	Code4	Code5	Code6	Total
Frequency	4	1	1	3	4	3	16
Percentage	25%	6%	6%	19%	25%	19%	100%

**10) If you were given the chance to leave to another school, would you go?
What would be the reason?**

- I. No, I got used to it
- II. No, I love my teachers
- III. No, it's the best school in the area
- IV. No, I'm very happy here / love this school
- V. No, high standard of education and support
- VI. No, I'm part of the school / family / home
- VII. Yes, lack of activities and a lot of pressure

Code List	Code1	Code2	Code3	Code4	Code5	Code6	Code 7	Total
Frequency	2	1	1	3	2	4	1	14
Percentage	14%	7%	7%	21%	14%	29%	7%	100%

APPENDIX D

LIST OF 30 QUESTIONS: INDEPENDENT AND DEPENDENT

Independent Variable

- P1. I feel EHS is my home.
- P2. I'm treated as an individual
- P3. I'm in good relationship with my teachers
- P4. Open, honest and active communication occurs between teachers-students, and teachers-parents
- P5. My family considers EHS warm, inviting and helpful.
- P6. My parents are proud of EHS results in the official exams
- P7. EHS has good reputation in the community
- P8. In the future, I will enroll my children at EHS
- PH9. Classrooms and grounds are clean and well-maintained
- PH10. School and classrooms are rich with displays of works created by students
- PH11. I'm satisfied with EHS library
- PH12. I'm satisfied with EHS playground
- PH13. I'm satisfied with EHS labs
- PH14. The canteen provides what I need.
- PH15. Students feel safe everywhere on EHS property
- PH16. EHS rules and regulations regarding safety and expected behavior are clear
- L17. Students are encouraged to succeed
- L18. Expectations are high for all students
- L19. EHS educational level is very high
- L20. Achievements and performance are rewarded, praised and publicly displayed
- L21. Students are assigned to research, prepare a presentation, and present in class
- L22. Progress is monitored, evaluated regularly, and shared with parents
- L23. I'm satisfied with afterschool activities
- L24. Teachers are caring and supportive
- L25. Classroom size and ratio of students-to-teacher are helpful to learning
- M26. EHS values diversity and is welcoming to all cultures
- M27. EHS has built my character with values and respect
- M28. Staff, students, and families demonstrate school pride
- M29. EHS and its educational program include development of knowledge/skills that promote ethical decision-making and conflict resolution

Dependent Variable

- M30. I'm satisfied with my experience at EHS
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